

ANALYSIS OF HISTORICAL OUTBREAKS OF
THE

BROWN LOCUST

Locustana pardalina (Walker, 1870)

OVER THE 45 YEAR PERIOD, 1960 TO 2005

Price, R.E and Kieser, M.E.

Insect Ecology Division, Agricultural Research Council, South Africa

Price, R.E and Kieser, M.E.
Insect Ecology Division, Agricultural Research
Council - Plant Health and Protection
Private Bag X134, Queenswood 0121, Pretoria,
South Africa.

Author contacts:

Price, R.E RogerEdwardPrice@gmail.com

Kieser, M.E. compugen@netactive.co.za

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Top right - Roosting adult swarm ©ARC

Bottom left - Large and densely roosting 5th instar gregarious 'rooibaadjie' hopper band ©ARC

Bottom right - Migrating adult swarm ©Dan Otte, 2011

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Abstract

The brown locust, *Locustana pardalina* (Walker), produces regular outbreaks within the semi-arid Nama Karoo biome of South Africa and southern Namibia. The historical records of outbreaks of the brown locust in South Africa date back to 1796, with a more detailed and continuous chronological history available in the literature from 1910 until the early 1960s. The current paper continues this chronological history for a further 45 years from 1960 until 2005 and confirms the very high frequency of annual outbreaks, with chemical control of gregarious brown locust populations being required in almost 90% of years somewhere or other within the outbreak area. Widespread and intense chemical control campaigns were required across at least 10 magisterial districts during a total of 26 seasons, which was 58% of the 45-year study period and highlights the frequency and scale of brown locust outbreaks. A total of 12 plague eruption events were documented during the study period, as defined when tens of thousands of hopper bands and >5 000 adult swarms were controlled per locust season.

The history of brown locust control in South Africa, as well as the locust control strategy and operational tactics are discussed. The climate and vegetation of the Nama Karoo is described and the biology and population dynamics of the brown locust are briefly summarised. The paper provides a comprehensive description and analysis of each of the annual outbreaks based directly on the Department of Agriculture's locust control records. Interrogating the prevailing rainfall conditions was key to understanding the location and dynamics of the annual outbreaks, while the efficacy of control operations during the different outbreak years also played a critical role. The description of outbreaks from 1960/61 until 1979/80 were mainly extracted from brief Government summary reports, while outbreaks from 1980/81 until 1993/94 were based on maps hand-drawn by locust researchers based on weekly locust control records per magisterial district. Outbreaks from 1994/95 until 2004/05 were based on a more detailed database of the number of locust control operations conducted per farm location per week, which was then mapped in ArcGIS per quarter-degree square. The ArcGIS mapping allowed the aggregated frequency of control operations per quarter degree square over the decade period to be determined throughout the outbreak area, which is an important indicator tool for potential environmental risk from repeated pesticide application.

Incipient brown locust outbreaks often occur simultaneously across a vast area of the Nama Karoo and such wide-scale eruptions are impossible to prevent. However, the chemical control campaigns waged against the brown locust on an almost annual basis have evidently not dampened the ability of this locust species to produce serious eruptions on a regular basis. While the control teams can effectively control the small and medium sized outbreaks, the control capacity is often overwhelmed during the large-scale outbreaks and it is usually the effect of mid-season drought conditions or the onset of winter conditions in the Karoo that brings the large outbreaks to an end. However, the ever-increasing economic costs of the control campaigns, as well as the environmental contamination that is inevitably caused by the application of broad-spectrum insecticides in the ecologically sensitive Nama Karoo biome is a cause for concern. Knowledge of the development and course of brown locust outbreaks is essential for understanding the outbreak dynamics of the locust and for improving plague

prevention. Analysis of past brown locust outbreaks, especially in relation to prevailing rainfall, is important to help to predict the likely seasonal movements of the population and where long-range swarm displacements are likely to end up. Effective control of migrant pests, such as locusts, relies heavily on advanced warnings of outbreaks in order to prepare for timeous and cost-effective control campaigns.

1. Introduction

The brown locust, *Locustana pardalina* (Walker), is the most economically important plague locust species in southern Africa and produces regular outbreaks within the semi-arid Karoo areas of South Africa and southern Namibia (Faure and Marais, 1937; Lea, 1958, 1968, 1969, Price, 2021). Historical records during the 20th century showed that gregarious outbreaks, requiring chemical control intervention, were combated somewhere or other in the Karoo in approximately 90% of the years (Lea, 1968, 1969; Price and Brown, 2000, Price 2021). However, the intensity of annual outbreaks varied greatly with the minor outbreaks comprising just a few scattered hopper bands compared with plague eruption seasons when tens of thousands of hopper band and adult swarms targets were controlled. Plague cycles during the 1920s and 1930s overran most of southern Africa as far north as the Zambezi River (Faure, 1932) and the locusts threatened crop production and the food security of the entire southern African region. The South African Government first officially intervened to assist farmers with the control of locusts on their farms in 1906 when they provided arsenic poison and spray pumps to the farmers (Lounsbury, 1906).

Due to the incessant plagues of red and brown locusts experienced in the early 1900s, the South African Government declared plague locusts as National Pests in 1911 in one of the first legislations promulgated by the new Government of the Union of South Africa (Lounsbury, 1915). The landowners then became legally responsible for reporting the presence of locusts on their land and for undertaking the actual spray operations, while the Government supplied the locust poison and spray pumps. However, the Government later agreed to pay the farmers and their farm workers for their labour in combatting the locusts. This long-standing legal agreement between the farmers and the Government was clarified in various amendments to the legislation, culminating in Article 6 of the South African Migratory Pests Act (Act No. 36 of 1983). An updated and consolidated policy specifically for the management of the locust problem in South Africa was gazetted in 1998 (DoA, 1998). Locusts are managed as a natural catastrophe, similar to drought or flood relief, with emergency funding being released by Government to manage the outbreaks. No technological early warning systems are in place and the locust control organisation relies on reactive intervention once the outbreaks are reported to avert further development to plague status. The brown locust control strategy in operation since 1906 in South Africa has been to protect the food security of the country by chemically controlling outbreaks at source on the Karoo farms before gregarious swarms can escape from the Karoo outbreak area to threaten the cereal cropping areas in the Free State and North West Provinces. After the organochlorine insecticide, benzene hexachloride (BHC) became available after 1945, this control strategy has been successful and the brown locust outbreaks have largely been confined to the Karoo. Short-term swarm invasions into the cereal crop production areas of South Africa and into surrounding countries have only occurred during the most intense plague eruptions and food security has not been seriously threatened (Lea, 1970; Price and Brown, 2000, Price 2021). The tactics of brown locust control have also not changed much

over the past century, known locally in the Karoo as the 'Commando system', with the Department of Agriculture dispatching mobile ground-control teams recruited on a temporary basis from the local farming communities in response to the reports of gregarious locust targets received from the Karoo landholders. The control teams are hired on a daily stipend and use private pick-up vehicles provided by the temporarily appointed locust officers/drivers, who are usually local farmers with previous locust control experience, supported by casual workers who do the actual spraying. The control teams usually operate in their local magisterial district where they know the local farms and road network. The teams are issued with stocks of insecticide (ultra-low (UL) formulation) and with motorised backpack and vehicle-mounted mist-blower spray machines, along with sufficient personal protective clothing. The number of control teams in operation during each outbreaks varies greatly, depending upon the location and extent of the outbreaks, but during large-scale outbreaks the emergency field situation may require the deployment of hundreds of often inexperienced control teams with limited pesticide application training.

The history of locust control methods and the various insecticides applied in South Africa has been described (Price, 2021). Most of the chemical control is focussed against the late instar (L4-L5) hopper bands, which roost densely at night on the low Karoo bushes (0.3-1.5m high) and form very conspicuous orange-brown targets that are visible in the morning sunshine from up to a kilometre or more away. Hopper bands are usually controlled shortly after sunrise while still densely clustered on their overnight roosting sites, or sometimes during the early evening while starting to roost on the vegetation. Once the hopper bands start to descend from their roosts in the morning and to march away, control becomes impractical. Hopper bands are controlled using the spot application of insecticide to relatively small areas using motorised backpack (mainly the Solo Port 423®) and vehicle mounted sprayers (mainly the Power Solo®) that simply use the air-blast to sheer and expel the insecticide droplets. These Solo air-blast machines are now considered obsolete and do not give a controlled droplet-size during application, as is provided with more modern spray machines. Most of the hopper band spray targets are small and discrete, measuring from 0.05 – 0.5 ha in extent, with >90% of targets smaller than 0.25 ha (Brown, 1988; Price, 2021). The average size of roosting adult swarms during the large outbreaks measured 14ha, with some large swarm targets roosting over an area of 2-3 km². However, most of the control is targeted against fledgling swarms that are relatively small at 1-5 ha in extent, usually roosting as a thick, silver-grey coloured blanket of insects covering the Karoo bushes and grass vegetation. The fledgling swarms often coalesce to form large, fast-flying migrating swarms that must be tracked by the mobile control teams during the day, sometimes over distances of >100 km to their overnight roosting spots. All swarm targets are sprayed during the night while roosting on the Karoo vegetation using vehicle-mounted motorized sprayers. This tactic allows more time to organise and coordinate the local control teams to undertake the spraying of these often large-size targets. The night-time spraying often occurs under atmospheric inversion conditions typical in the Karoo, especially during the cool autumn season, which sometimes causes application problems with inadequate insecticide drift and sub-optimum impaction of the insecticide droplets. Spray aircraft and spray helicopters are only employed during emergencies when the ground teams are becoming overwhelmed, being used to control the largest of the swarm targets within the high-intensity outbreak areas and to bolster the campaign to intercept swarm escapes from the Karoo. Such swarm targets are also directly sprayed in the early morning whilst on their roosts. No air-to-air application tactics are employed against flying swarms.

1.1. Nama Karoo biome

The outbreak area of the brown locust falls mainly within the Nama Karoo biome (Low & Rebelo, 1996), which occupies the extensive central plateau of the western half of South Africa at an altitude of 500–2000 m, and into southern Namibia. The Nama Karoo is South Africa's third-largest biome, covering an area of >135 000 km², and contains three bioregions, namely, the Bushmanland, Upper Karoo, and the Lower Karoo Bioregions, with 14 recognised vegetation types (Low & Rebelo, 1996). The climate of the Karoo has been summarized by Desmet and Cowling (1999). The region experiences significant temperature fluctuations, with hot summers with maximum temperatures of >40 °C being common in many areas, while winters can be cold and minimum temperatures can drop well below 0°C, with frost being common at Karoo altitudes. The rainfall across the outbreak area mainly falls in late summer and autumn as thundershowers, with a rainfall gradient ranging from approximately 100-130 mm in the arid northwestern areas, to approximately 380-400 mm per annum in the eastern Karoo, although rainfall patterns are typically erratic and extended droughts are common (Hoffman & Cowling, 1990; Desmet and Cowling, 1999).

Most of the Nama Karoo ecoregion is defined as arid and semi-arid natural rangeland that has not been transformed for crop agriculture or lost to urban development. Most of the vegetation types and the integrity of the range of ecosystems found across the Nama Karoo are therefore still largely intact (Mucina and Rutherford, 2006). Vegetation is dominated by arid and semi-arid dwarf shrublands and open grasslands on poor, lime-rich, shallow and stoney soils over rock (Cowling & Roux, 1987), with a mixed vegetation of grasses, succulents, geophytes and annual forbs (Acocks, 1988). The mix of palatable Karoo bushes and desert grasses is extensively utilised for sheep and goat grazing (for meat, wool and pelts), although the annual vegetation production and carrying capacity for stock animals is generally low. However, extensive areas of the Karoo vegetation have been severely overgrazed and degraded over the past 150 years by the selective feeding by sheep and goats. Although average stocking rates are now kept to more sustainable levels on most farms, many of the historically degraded areas will probably take many decades to rehabilitate, if this is at all possible, with long-term detrimental impacts on the ecological process and biodiversity carrying capacity in these areas.

Less than 1% of the Nama Karoo biome is conserved in formal areas, such as the Karoo National Park and the Mountain Zebra National Park. However, there are numerous other privately-owned farms and 'conservancy areas' that are reserved for Karoo nature tourism and for game hunting. There are also a few initiatives in which non-profit organisations have partnered with landowners to bring about sustainable land management and to maintain the integrity of the Karoo ecosystem, such as The Endangered Wildlife Trust's Drylands Conservation Programme. The invertebrate fauna of the Nama Karoo is still poorly known (SANBI, 2020), apart from perhaps the butterflies, dragonflies and grasshoppers where representative museum collections and taxonomic literature are available. For example, the species-rich Karoo grasshopper fauna is characterised by a high proportion of apterous and endemic species (Stewart, 1998; Gebeyehu and Samways, 2003), which would possibly suggest that many more unique invertebrate species are likely to be found in this ancient ecoregion, but there is insufficient data to be able to identify endemics with any certainty and the threat status of most invertebrate groups has not been assessed according to International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) criteria. The reptile and amphibian fauna of the Karoo is well known, but the degree of endemism is low when compared with

the adjacent succulent Karoo biome (Tolley, *et. al.*, 2023). However, certain areas of the Nama-Karoo, such as the Karoo National Park, has a comparatively rich biodiversity of reptiles and amphibians with 68 species recorded (Branch & Braack, 1987). Under the Global 200 ecoregion classification (Olson and Dinerstein, 1998), the Nama Karoo is listed as one of the 136 global terrestrial ecoregions considered as priority for conservation based on its biological distinctiveness (species richness and endemism), being classified as Critical/Endangered (Mittermeier, 1998, 2004). The Nama Karoo deserts and shrublands are one of the 12 ecoregions under the Global 200 classification where insecticide application for locust control is a concern (Peveling, 2001). In addition, part of the invasion area of the brown locust lies within the adjacent succulent Karoo biome in the Western Cape, which is considered as a global biodiversity hot-spot where large numbers of endemic and endangered species are found (Mittermeier, 1998, 2004; Peveling, 2001).

1.2. Biology and outbreak dynamics of the brown locust

The biology and population dynamics of the brown locust have been studied in detail in the laboratory and field (Faure, 1923; Potgieter, 1929; Du Plessis, 1938, 1939; Smit, 1939, 1960; Lea, 1953, 1968, 1969). The literature has been thoroughly reviewed by Henschel *et. al.* (2015, 2023) and by Price (2021, 2023). The brown locust displays a strong and distinct phase polymorphism and can be readily found in the Karoo in three phase types, namely the solitary phase (grasshopper type) at low population densities, transient phase (which is population density dependent and is the behavioral and morphometrical transition from the solitary phase towards a more gregarious phase, and vice versa), and then the gregarious phase that develops at high and crowded population densities (Faure, 1932). The true 'extreme' gregarious phase, as described by Faure (1932) and available as museum specimens with its larger body size and highly constricted pronotum, has not been seen since the plague swarming populations of the 1930s when gregarious swarms could repeatedly reproduce unhindered by chemical control. The brown locust has a multivoltine lifecycle, producing 2-3 generations between the months of September to May if there is well-distributed rainfall (Smit, 1939), with 4 generations per outbreak season recorded on rare occasions (Lea, 1958, Price 2021). The brown locust will lay its eggs indiscriminately in moist or dry soil, with the solitary phase females preferring well-drained sandy/loam soils on sloping ground that is well drained. Gregarious swarms tend to be less discerning in their choice of oviposition sites, but both phases will totally avoid the silt/clay pan areas for oviposition. Egg pods hatch under warm soil temperatures (usually between September and April in the Karoo) following sufficient rainfall to enable egg development. The solitary phase adults lay eggs that have an obligate diapause, which is usually broken after 9-45 days under dry conditions, while the gregaria phase only lays non-diapause eggs that develop continuously to hatching under warm and wet conditions (Matthee, 1951). Interestingly, the transient phase females lay egg pods containing differing proportions of diapause and non-diapause eggs. Under extended dry conditions all brown locust eggs can enter a state of quiescence during which they are very tolerant to desiccation. Solitary phase eggs have been known to survive for 2-3 years under drought conditions in the field with egg populations gradually building up in the soil (Potgieter, 1929; Botha, 1967; Price, *pers. obs.*), although Botha (1967) dismissed any eggs surviving for more than 12 months as being largely irrelevant to the population dynamics of the brown locust. Some eggs can hatch in the field after receiving as little as 10 mm rainfall, but an effective rainfall of 15-25 mm is necessary for the widespread hatching of eggs (Smit, 1939).

The relationship between rainfall patterns in the Karoo and the development of brown locust outbreaks is not clear and has been the subject of a range of studies. Lea (1958) suggested that the early summer rainfall (July-December) conditions during two or more seasons preceding significant population upsurges was the key factor, with relatively dry early summers favoring locust breeding in the long term, and wet early summers usually causing a decrease in populations. Population increases or decreases were not correlated with the late summer rainfall, or for the season as a whole (Lea, 1958). However, other studies could find no statistical evidence of any connection between brown locust eruptions and previous austral winter rainfall (Todd, *et. al.*, 2002), but instead found a high correlation between rainfall over the previous 12 months prior to the locust season and especially with rainfall during December. The hypothesis was that the high-frequency outbreak cycles were related to the El Niño/Southern Oscillation (ENSO) climatic patterns and that high-frequency locust activity was clearly evident during La Niña events (wet cycles in southern Africa) and with low locust activity during El Niño dry events. A dominant outbreak frequency of 17.3 years was proposed, with these extended cycles strongly related to the sea-surface temperatures and ENSO events (Todd, *et. al.*, 2002). However, the historical records suggest that large-scale brown locust outbreaks have often occurred following heavy and widespread rains in the Karoo that have broken an extended drought spell. The clear association of the impact of drought-breaking rains and the development of large-scale outbreaks was also confirmed by Nailand and Hahrahan (1993).

The annual outbreaks of the brown locust occur during the warmer months of the year when temperature and rainfall conditions are suitable for grass growth and locust development. Depending upon rainfall, locust control operations can start as early as September in spring and then persist through the austral summer season until May-June of the late autumn and early winter in the following year. The outbreak area of the brown locust generally lies within the recognized summer-rainfall area of the country, and the Karoo winters are too cold and dry for any hoppers or adults to survive through the winter season. Throughout the Karoo, the brown locust population can only survive the winter season as diapause or quiescent overwintering eggs in the soil. However, hoppers and adults certainly can survive winter in warmer areas of the invasion range of the locust, as recorded in the past in the Central Kalahari Desert of Botswana and throughout the northeastern areas of South Africa and into Zimbabwe (Faure, 1932; Price, 2023).

1.3. Outbreak area of the brown locust

The outbreak area of the brown locust was first delimited by Faure & Marais (1937) but was later re-defined by Lea (1958) based on analysis of the expenditure on locust control in each magisterial district in the Karoo over a 25-year period between 1933 – 1958, with districts showing a low, medium and high outbreak frequency identified (Fig. 1). The highest frequency of annual outbreaks during this period occurred in the Hopetown and De Aar magisterial districts in the Upper Central Karoo and in the Middelburg district in the eastern Karoo (Lea, 1958) (Fig. 1). The boundaries of the outbreak area were later re-defined by Kieser, Thackrah and Rosenberg (2002) based on additional outbreak records during the 1980s and 1990s and will be discussed later in the text.

Fig. 1. The outbreak area of the brown locust as defined by Lea (1958). Magisterial districts and the location of major towns are provided for reference. The 100mm, 200mm, 400mm and 500mm mean rainfall isohyets are also shown for reference.

1.4. Outbreak cycles

Outbreak cycles of the brown locust generally start with the development of incipient outbreaks that are characterized by the dramatic and largely synchronized increase in the density of solitary phase adult populations over a wide area of the Karoo, leading to the crowding of locusts and phase transformation of hatching hoppers (Du Plessis, 1938; Smit, 1939; Smit, 1941; Lea, 1968, Lea, 1969). During wide-scale incipient outbreaks, the development of incipient swarming populations leading to rapid aggregation and gregarisation of the hoppers is often synchronized across hundreds of farms in the brown locust outbreak area in an unstoppable eruptive process that we don't yet understand. Numerous gregarious phase hopper bands and swarms are then produced, with the eruption rapidly expanding and intensifying into plague status that can then persist over a number of successive years. Although intensive chemical control measures may contain the outbreaks within the Karoo, it is believed that drought spells and the deteriorating availability of green food to maintain successful reproduction is the main environmental driver that forces swarming activity to collapse into a period of relative inactivity again (Smit, 1938; Lea, 1958).

Lounsbury (1915) investigated the historical records of brown locust outbreaks between 1796 and 1910 and described a distinct outbreak periodicity of approximately 13 years of great swarming activity alternating with quiet periods of approximately 11 years of relatively low locust activity. The historical record was continued by Du Plessis (1937, 1939), who described outbreaks between 1910-1939, followed by the more detailed analysis of Lea (1958, 1968) for the period 1942-1954 and 1954-1964 respectively. Lea (1968) observed that the periodicity of outbreak cycles from 1910 to 1964 had shortened, with swarming periods of 7-11 years alternating with similar periods of comparatively low locust activity. The hypothesis was that the shortening of the outbreak periodicity coincided with the introduction of the Government's chemical control operations which prevent the full evacuation of the swarms from the outbreak area, as previously occurred when migrating brown locust swarms invaded large areas of southern Africa (Lea, 1968; De Villiers, 1988). During chemical control operations, a proportion of the swarming populations inevitably escape being controlled each season and are retained in the Karoo to continue breeding which leads to new outbreaks continuing on a regular basis without allowing the swarming locust population to 'boil over' and to completely evacuate the outbreak area (Lea, 1968, De Villiers, 1988). The inevitable conclusion was that chemical control operations against the brown locust were, in fact, exacerbating the locust problem and causing more frequent outbreaks that required regular chemical control.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Brown locust outbreak information obtained from DoA-Technical Services Annual reports, 1960/61 to 1979/80

After Arnold Lea (1969) had published the detailed chronological records of the brown locust outbreaks from 1954/55 until the end of the 1963/64 season, no further records of subsequent outbreaks are available, apart from very brief summaries as found in the Annual Reports of the South African Department of Agriculture-Technical Services (annual reports written in Afrikaans and translated into English below). However, it was important to capture this historical outbreak information for the period after 1963/1964 (post Lea), as available in

the annual report summaries from 1964/65 to 1979/80 to continue the chronological outbreak records. A more comprehensive analysis of outbreaks started from the 1980/81 season when more comprehensive locust control information became available.

2.2. Brown locust control reports and mapping of outbreaks, 1980/81 to 1993/94

During the period 1980-1983, reports of brown locust control operations undertaken by the National Department of Agriculture (NDA) locust officers in the Karoo were made available (Isak Venter, Chief Locust Officer, NDA, Pretoria). Some field observations were also undertaken from 1983 by the newly formed locust research unit of the Plant Protection Research Institute (PPRI), Pretoria, under the leadership of Dr. H.D. Brown. However, starting in the 1984/85 season, monthly summary reports of locust control operations undertaken against brown locust hopper band and adult swarm targets in the Karoo were received directly by faximile by the PPRI Locust Unit from the main locust control depots which recorded the number of vehicle-mounted control teams active in each "locust" district in the previous month, as well as the number of hopper bands and adult swarms controlled by these teams in each district. The "locust" districts were used as a management tool by the NDA to arbitrarily split up some of the larger magisterial districts, such as Kenhardt and Gordonia, into smaller areas to aid locust management reporting and logistics. However, the boundaries of the 'locust management districts' were not always compatible with the boundaries of the official magisterial districts, which then required transformation of some of the 'locust district' data to match official magisterial boundaries.

After 1988, however, the locust control information received from the NDA was more comprehensive and recorded the control operations undertaken on individual farms, summarized as weekly records per magisterial district, as well as the estimated size of hopper bands and swarms controlled. The detailed analysis and interpretation of specific outbreaks sometimes required more information than was available in the control reports, so additional details were then obtained during telephone conversations with locust officers, or during visits to the main locust control depots in De Aar, Upington and Kimberley. Staff from the PPRI Locust Research Unit were also regular visitors to the Karoo during each of the 1986-1996 outbreak seasons and were able to witness and record detailed aspects of these outbreaks, such as the intensity and efficacy of the control operations, the development stage of the locusts on specific dates, and the direction of swarm displacements. Hand-drawn maps of the development of each annual outbreak were then generated using as much field information as could be obtained from the various sources.

2.3. Brown locust control reports and ArcGIS mapping of outbreaks, 1994/95 to 2004/05

For the period 1994/95 to 2004/05, an Excel database was created to capture the hand-written records of locust control operations received by faximile at PPRI on a weekly basis directly from the NDA locust control depots at De Aar and Upington. These faximile records provided a 'locust district', a farm name, and the weekly total of number of hopper bands and adult swarms controlled on each farm. Farm names were allocated to a quarter degree ($\frac{1}{4}^{\circ}$) grid reference by locating the farm on a 1:250,000 paper map, and then entering farm name, farm number, and the respective $\frac{1}{4}$ degree reference (= LOCUS) into the Excel database. Week numbers were allocated to each calendar year, starting at 1 January and ending 31

December. This databasing exercise was funded by the United Kingdom Department for International Development (DFID) from 2000 to 2003. An example of a row entry in this database is given Table 1.

Table 1. Example of the row entry in the locust database.

DISTRICT	WEEKNO	FARMNAME	NUMBER	LOCUS	HOPPERBANDSSWARMS
Namaqualand	1	Volstruishoek	88	2919AC	1 0

Note that for the purpose of this study we refer to the old historical names of magisterial districts in the Karoo as used in the locust control database up until 2005. Names of magisterial districts and local municipalities have since changed under the Department of Constitutional Development in South Africa, along with some boundary changes. For example, the Northern Cape Province is now divided, for local Government purposes, into five district municipalities: Frances Baard, ZF Mgcawu, John Taolo Gaetsewe, Namakwa, and Pixley Ka Seme, which in turn are divided into 26 local municipalities.

The locust control database was then mapped using the ArcGIS map version 10.6.1, QGIS version 3.22.5 and Python version 3.9 software's for data preparation, manipulation and presentation of the results. The LOCUS database was mapped to a $\frac{1}{4}$ degree grid map of the Karoo using the LOCUS reference identification numbers. This was done in QGIS using the '*join by attribute*' function. To calculate the intensity of both hopper bands and swarms per $\frac{1}{4}$ degree over the period, a vertical summation was performed in Python after generating a stacked geodatabase of the seasonal datasets. Furthermore, ArcGIS was used to generate the spatial distribution of the controlled locust.

2.4. Sub-division of the outbreak area

To describe locust outbreaks occurring in different parts of the outbreak region, Lea (1969) divided the Karoo and surrounding areas impacted by brown locusts into six sub-divisions, or sub-regions, according to the typical rainfall patterns and vegetation types found in these specific sub-regions. Lea also considered these sub-regions as a convenient division of the outbreak area in relation to the ecology and topography of these areas, as well as in relation to the typical outbreak patterns observed (Lea, 1969). These sub-regions have now been simplified where possible to follow the boundaries of magisterial districts, and to amalgamate Lea's 'Central' and 'South-Central' areas into a single 'Central' sub-region. Therefore, in the study describing outbreaks from 1980/81 to 2004/05 where more detailed information on the locality of outbreaks is available, a total of five sub-regions were defined within the outbreak area, namely the western, northern, southern, eastern and central sub-regions (Fig.2).

Fig 2. Division of the brown locust outbreak area into five geographical ‘sub-regions’

2.5. Rainfall data

Monthly rainfall data for 36 rainfall stations distributed throughout the brown locust outbreak region was obtained for 1980-2004 from the SA Weather Bureau, Pretoria. Only the stations in each sub-region with a complete history of rainfall data for the entire study period were included. The rainfall stations (listed below) were grouped according to their locality in the five sub-regions of the Karoo as defined in Fig. 2 above.

Western sub-region: Brandvlei, Calvinia, Carnarvon, Groblershoop, Kenhardt, Marydale, Noenieput, Pofadder, Upington, Van Wyksvlei, Wiliston.

Central sub-region: Britstown, De Aar, Hopetown, Philipstown, Prieska, Richmond, Niekerkshoop, Strydenburg, Victoria West.

Eastern sub-region: Colesberg, Cradock, Koffiefontein, Middelburg, Nouport, Petrusville, Phillopolis.

Southern sub-region: Beaufort West, Fraserburg, Graaff Reinett, Laingsburg, Willowmore.

Northern sub-region: Danielskuil, Griquatown, Olifansthoek, Postmasburg.

Following the detailed study of Lea (1969) on the influence of rainfall on locust outbreaks, the same biennial rainfall criteria defined by Lea were applied in the present study. Monthly rainfall figures for each station were therefore totalled for the six-month period, 1 July – 31 December, designated as the 'early season' (ES) period, and then for the six-month period, 1 January – 30 June, as the 'late season' (LS) for each year. The mean early season and mean late season rainfall totals for the stations occurring in each of the five sub-regions, were then used to classify the early and late rainfall seasons in these areas according to the rainfall indices defined by Lea (1969) (Table 2). Long-term rainfall data from the Karoo show that the ES rainfall is less and much more variable than during the LS period, with approximately 66% of the annual rainfall occurring during the late summer and autumn period (Lea, 1958; 1969; present study). Rainfall classification totals for the late season are thus twice that for the early season (Table 2). Even within a relatively wet season, the quantity, distribution and timing of rainfall in the Karoo is known to be very erratic, which typically leads to a patchy distribution of outbreaks. However, the calculation of the mean seasonal rainfall indices for stations falling within each sub-region of the Karoo at least provides an indication of the general rainfall situation across each sub-region.

Table 2. Classification of rainfall indices during the Early Season and Late Season in five sub-regions of the brown locust outbreak area across the Karoo (adapted from Lea, 1969).

Classification of rainfall during the Early Season and Late Season periods	Total rainfall recorded for early season (ES) (1 July – 31 December)	Total rainfall recorded for late season (LS) (1 January – 30 June)
Very dry	<50mm	<100mm
Dry	51-80mm	101-160mm
Medium (Normal)	81-120mm	161-240mm
Wet	121-160mm	241-320mm
Very wet	>160mm	>320mm

ES = winter, spring and early summer months (July – December).

LS = late summer, autumn and early winter months (January – June).

3. Results: Part 1 (DoA–Technical Services annual report summaries - 1960/61 to 1983/84)

Lea (1969) provided detailed chronological records of the brown locust outbreaks from 1954/55 until the 1963/64 season. From 1964 onwards, no further publications describing subsequent outbreaks are available apart from very brief summary reports of subsequent brown locust outbreaks found in the Annual Reports of the South African Department of Agriculture - Technical Services (annual reports written in Afrikaans and translated into English below). However, it is important to recap the incipient locust build-up from 1960 to the 1963/64 plague outbreak event as described by Lea (1969), followed by the DoA-Technical Services annual report summaries that described outbreaks from 1964/65 up until 1983/84.

3.1. 1960/61 season

No control operations. Lea (1969) reported an increase in the populations of solitary phase adults (known locally in Afrikaans as 'opbouers' (translation = to build up)) compared with the previous season. The forecast was that incipient swarming was likely to begin over the next few seasons.

3.2. 1961/62 season

Lea (1969) reported that an unexpected small outbreak occurred on one farm in the Jansenville district in the southern region. The gradual increase in the 'opbouer' populations was reported across a wide area of the Karoo, especially in the Griekwastad and Hopetown area in the central and northeastern areas, as well as in the Graff-Reinette and Aberdeen area in the southern sub-region. Control costs were negligible.

3.3. 1962/63 season

Lea (1969) described a widespread incipient outbreak that occurred across 23 districts in South Africa and an additional eight districts in southern Namibia, giving 31 districts in total. The dry early summer helped the control teams to contain the localised first-generation outbreak, but good rainfall during January 1963 triggered a widespread outbreak that persisted throughout the late summer and autumn of 1963. The control campaign was mainly focussed in the central and western sub-regions, but outbreaks were also combatted in the southern Karoo. Locust officers reported that numerous egg beds had been laid by swarms into winter of 1963 and a large campaign was forecast for the following season. Control costs in South Africa were given as R350 000. No figures for the number of hopper bands and swarms controlled were provided by Lea (1969) or in the DoA Technical services annual report.

3.4. 1963/64 season

Lea (1969) considered that the plague outbreak that occurred during the spring and early summer of 1963 was the most serious brown locust outbreak since 1950/51, with a widespread and intense early season outbreak occurring across the Karoo from October until December 1963. The control campaign was waged in 35 magisterial districts across the Karoo and into southern Namibia, with control of migrating swarms occurring in a least an additional 17-19 districts, giving a total of 54 magisterial districts at the maximum extent of the outbreak. An estimated total of >200 000 hopper bands and >20 000 swarms were controlled during this plague eruption. Some of the migrating swarms coalesced to form exceptionally large targets for control operations (Cilliers, Lea and van Someren Greeve, *et. al.*, 1964). A total of 250 motorized ground control units and 10 spray aircraft were used during control operations, with the costs of the campaign given as R750 000. However, the control campaign seemed to have been remarkably successful and no further gregarious outbreaks were reported after Christmas 1963 (Lea, 1969), although a number of migrating swarms were apparently lost as they flew north and disappeared into the remote Kalahari Desert in Botswana. The late season of 1963/64 (January-June 1964) was dry across the Karoo and these drought conditions would have also suppressed any further outbreaks. No locust outbreaks were reported during the late summer of 1964.

3.5. 1964/65 season

Following the dry late summer and autumn of 1964, the 1964/65 locust season remained dry across much of the Karoo. However, some of the migrating swarms from the previous 1963/64 outbreak had laid egg beds and a small-scale hopper control campaign was waged in summer 1964-1965 against hatching bands as they emerged from over-wintering egg beds in four magisterial districts, namely Postmasburg, Griekwastad, Prieska and in the eastern part of the Kenhardt district. A total of 323 hopper bands were controlled in these four districts. There are no records of any swarms being controlled. Later in the summer of 1965 there were reports of scattered solitaria-phase adults ('opbouers') in the Central Karoo, with small concentrations of adult locusts controlled on a few farms in the Richmond district. However, locust populations over most of the Karoo remained very low into the autumn and no gregarious outbreaks were forecast for the following summer season.

3.6. 1965/66 season

There were no records of any locust activity in the Karoo, and no control was conducted during the entire season. Field surveys conducted in the Central Karoo (De Aar region) during summer revealed that the populations of solitaria phase adults were very low and the locust population was considered to be in recession throughout the Karoo.

3.7. 1966/67 season

No locusts were reported during spring and early summer 1966, but incipient outbreaks of transient phase hoppers occurred from late summer and into autumn 1967, with the outbreak being focussed within the Douglas and Prieska districts, as well as in the Jacobsdal and Koffiefontein districts in the south-western Free State. The scale of this incipient outbreak was unexpected, and the locust control organisation was caught off-guard as the scattered late-instar hoppers rapidly congregated into marching bands and began to form fledgling adult swarms. Locust control operations were conducted in a total of 20 magisterial districts during the 1966/67 outbreak, with up to 86 motorised control teams being employed at the height in the campaign when the focus switched to the numerous adult swarm concentrations. The unusually cool and wet autumn season of April, May and early June also hampered the location and control of the adult concentrations, with many swarms maturing and laying egg-nests before they could be controlled. A total of 13 129 hopper bands and 6 412 adult swarms were controlled, using 514 tons of 7% gamma BHC dusting powder and 17 502 gallons of 10% gamma BHC emulsion. Widespread populations of non-swarmling solitary phase 'opbouer' adult populations were observed over a wide area of the Colesberg, Middelburg, Hofmeyr and Cradock districts in the eastern Karoo, with a forecast of widespread egg-laying before winter and an impending incipient outbreak for the following season.

3.8. 1967/68 season

As expected, a widespread outbreak occurred in the early summer of 1967/68 across a total of 33 magisterial districts in the Karoo, with the most intense localized outbreaks occurring in the western Free State Province and in the Douglas, Hopetown and Philipstown districts of the Cape Province during November and December 1967. The outbreak was considered to be exceptionally heavy in these eastern Karoo districts and developed to plague proportions, but the locust control organization had been well prepared for the impending outbreak. A total of 234 motorized control units and five light spray aircraft were used in the control campaign. A total of approximately 90 000 hopper bands and 3 000 adult swarms were controlled during the 1967/68 outbreak season, using a total of 879 tons of 7% gamma BHC powder, 44 429 gallons of 10% gamma BHC emulsion and 4 458 gallons of 15% gamma BHC emulsion. However, a severe late summer drought from late January to April 1968 prevented another locust generation from developing and the outbreak rapidly subsided.

3.9. 1968/69 season

Good early rains favored a rapid buildup of solitary populations in early summer, with widespread non-swarmling adult populations being observed which evidently did not form controllable targets. A small outbreak occurred in the Fauresmith magisterial district from mid-November until early December 1968, with a total of 1 008 hopper bands being controlled by three control teams. Dry summer conditions prevented any further outbreaks. Good autumn rains fell in March and April 1969 over a wide area of the Karoo. Hopper populations were reported from districts in the eastern Karoo, but they did not aggregate into dense bands that made control impractical and not cost-effective, apart from six small hopper bands controlled in the Fauresmith district in the first week of April. A total of 18 adult swarm concentrations were later controlled in the same Fauresmith district. Widespread adult concentrations at sub-control densities were reported across the eastern Karoo in

April-May and were expected to lay eggs before winter. A widespread outbreak was therefore expected for the following season.

3.10. 1969/70 season

The spring and early summer were very dry and the first rains in October 1969 were too light and scattered to initiate a widespread outbreak. However, from late October, isolated hopper outbreaks occurred on farms in eight districts, namely, the Fauresmith, Koffiefontein and Philipstown districts in the eastern Karoo and in the Middelburg, Hofmeyr, Graaff-Reinet and Aberdeen districts in the south-eastern Karoo. A total of 12 adult swarms were also apparently controlled near Lady Frere (Transkei) in the current Chris Hani District of the Eastern Cape Province, which was the first time that locusts had been controlled in this area since the 1930s. It is not recorded whether these locusts developed locally or flew into the Lady Frere area. A second generation developed in summer 1970, with the height of control campaign occurring in February 1970 when 11 control teams were in operation in seven magisterial districts (Kimberly, Fauresmith, Petrusburg, Boshoff, Jacobsdal, Douglas and Hopetown). The last of the fledgling swarms were controlled in April in the Douglas district. A total of 3 464 hopper bands and 377 adult swarms were controlled during the 1969/70 outbreak season, using 34 369 kg of 7% gamma BHC powder and 15 038 liters of 10% gamma BHC emulsion.

3.11. 1970/71 season

Good widespread rains enabled an intense brown locust outbreak to develop over a wide area of the Karoo from October-November 1970, which rapidly overwhelmed the control campaign and developed into the largest plague since the 1950/51 outbreak. Large-scale control campaigns were conducted throughout the northwestern Cape into Bushmanland, the Central Karoo and into the southwestern Free State and down into the eastern and southeastern Karoo. Numerous swarms escaped the Karoo and were tracked down and controlled in the Free State and North West Provinces, as well as into the interior of the Eastern Cape Province. Most of the Karoo was infested with gregarious populations and migrating swarms escaped from the outbreak area into surrounding districts, giving a large total of >70 magisterial districts that required locust control operations. A total of 402 control units and 16 aircraft were employed during the campaign. An estimated >200 000 hopper bands and >30 000 swarms were controlled, although further details of the control campaign are not available. The cost of the campaign was given at R1.5 million.

3.12. 1971/72 season

With the continuation of the plague cycle that started the previous season, an intensive outbreak developed in October 1971 from the overwintering egg beds laid by swarms during the previous autumn of 1971. Control operations were soon overwhelmed and by 18 November 1971 a total of 296 control teams were active in 64 magisterial districts. Control operations continued throughout December and a widespread second generation developed by mid-January 1972. A third generation developed and during April and May 1972, but on a much reduced scale. Some migration of swarms into the Northern Cape Province from the south was reported in the second half of May. A total of 186 005 hopper bands and 5 214 adult swarms were controlled during the 1971/72 outbreak season, using 1 957 metric tons of BHC dusting powder and 43 200 liters of emulsifiable BHC concentrate. The detailed

costs of the campaign were given as R368 207 for labour, R194 763 for transport costs, R608 326 for the insecticide, R118 174 for maintenance and aerial surveys used. The total cost of the locust control campaign was given as R1 289 470.

3.13. 1972/73 season

Relatively dry conditions prevailed over most of the Karoo and the expected continuation of the plague cycle experienced over the previous two seasons did not materialize. Only small-scale outbreaks were reported in late October and early November 1972 from the Koffiefontein and Fauresmith and Herbert (Douglas) districts in the eastern Karoo, but only two control teams were required. Outbreaks on a greater scale occurred in March 1973 in the Kenhardt district in the vicinity of Pofadder town where eight control teams were in action. Control was undertaken in only four magisterial districts during the 1972/73 season.

3.14. 1973/74 season

Heavy rains were recorded across the Karoo in the early season (spring) of 1973, causing a widespread hopper outbreak to begin from mid-September onwards. The exceptionally heavy outbreak soon got out of control in many areas and the locust control capacity could not cope with the number of swarms that came onto the wing. By the end of May 1974, control operations had been conducted in a total of 51 magisterial districts with a total of 429 motorized control teams employed at the peak infestation, along with five spray aircraft to combat swarm escapes. A total of 2 500 metric tons of BHC dusting powder and 106 000 liters concentrate organophosphate insecticide were used during the campaign. A total of 151 437 hopper band targets and 35 203 roosting swarms were controlled, with hopper control still going on until 22 June in the Sutherland district. The campaign was characterized by the failure to control the hopper outbreak due to shortage of resources and manpower at the start of the outbreak before many thousands of adult swarms had come onto the wing. The wet conditions also caused problems with accessibility to flooded areas to undertake control operations.

3.15. 1974/75 season

A lot of overwintering egg beds were reported from the migrating swarms in autumn and early winter 1974 and a large control campaign was expected throughout the Karoo for the 1974/75 season, so the locust control organization had more time to prepare over the winter period. The first hatching hoppers were reported on 20 September 1974 and a widespread hopper infestation soon developed across at least 31 magisterial districts. The height of the control campaign occurred during November 1974 when 394 control teams and four spray aircraft were employed, especially to track down and control the swarms before they could escape from the Karoo. The outbreak subsided dramatically by early January 1975, and only small outbreaks were then observed up until March 1975 which were readily controlled. During the 1974/75 campaign, a total of 168 406 hopper bands and 5 460 adult swarms were controlled, using a total of 1 283 metric tons of BHC dusting powder, 12 575 liters of emulsifiable concentrate (EC) and 2 000 liters of a ULV formulation (presumably organophosphate). Concern was raised about the continuous application of the persistent BHC production in the Karoo and active development of new ULV ground spraying equipment was initiated with prototype machines first tested. The total costs of the locust campaign, including insecticide stocks, personnel costs and vehicle mileage was given as

R1 487 409. The 1974/75 campaign was considered a success as the intense and better organized campaign against the hopper bands in November 1974 greatly reduced the number of swarms coming onto the wing, as compared with the ratio of the number of swarms produced during the previous 1973/74 outbreak.

3.16. 1975/76 season

The reduced locust activity recorded in the autumn of 1975 continued into spring of 1975 and no gregarious outbreaks were reported before New Year 1976. However, relatively high populations of solitaria phase 'opbouer' adults were reported by the locust officers in many areas of the western and central Karoo, but the adult concentrations were at a density that were uneconomic for control operations. These locusts evidently bred during January and February 1976 during wet conditions and widespread incipient outbreaks then resulted, starting in the Williston district on 10 February 1976 and soon expanding to an additional ten districts, namely Calvinia, Carnarvon, Fraserburg, Gordonia (Kakamas area only), Kenhardt, Namaqualand, Prieska, Sutherland, Vanrhynsdorp and Victoria West (Vosburg area). However, many of the control teams reported that the control operations were difficult and time-consuming as many of the targets were not fully gregarised, forming numerous small and scattered targets comprising mixed-instar hoppers that did not form strongly marching bands. Adult swarms were also scattered and did not form concentrated targets. The control campaign continued until 24 May in the Loeriesfontein area of the Calvinia district. However, locust officers were concerned that large areas containing diffuse adult concentrations had escaped control and would lay eggs before winter. During the 1975/76 control campaign, a total of 76 control teams were employed in 11 magisterial districts, with a total of 18 627 hopper targets and 3 659 adult swarms controlled. A total of 185 000 kg of BHC dusting powder was applied. Field-testing of the new ULV spraying machines (locally designed stacked spinning discs) continued.

3.17. 1976/77 season

The first control operations started on 13 September 1976 in the Vanrhynsdorp district. The hopper outbreak expanded rapidly in the central and western Karoo and control operations reached a peak in November 1976, with a total of 13 districts infested, namely, Beaufort-West, Britstown, Calvinia, Carnarvon, Fraserburg, Hopetown, Kenhardt, Prieska, Namaqualand (Springbok area) Sutherland, Vanrhynsdorp, Victoria-West and Williston. A maximum of 78 control teams were employed during November 1976. The intense control campaign against this 1st generation of hoppers and fledgling adults was successful, and the campaign was concluded by Christmas 1976. The locust situation was then quiet until a small outbreak was controlled between the end of February and early April 1977 in the Carnarvon district only. During the 1976/77 campaign, a total of 18 980 hopper bands and 1 344 adult swarms were controlled, using 221 520 kg of 7% gamma-BHC dusting powder.

3.18. 1977/78 season

The first control operation against hatching hopper bands was reported on 4 October 1977 in the Carnarvon district, with new hatchings then reported throughout October across the Britstown, Hay (Griekwastad), Hopetown, Kenhardt, Philistown, Prieska and Victoria west districts. The hopper control operation was unable to prevent some swarms coming onto the wing from late November onwards, which then laid eggs to produce a 2nd generation in January 1978. The outstanding feature of the outbreak was the number of very large and

fast-flying migrating swarms that developed in early January 1978 in the remote and sparsely populated area of the southwestern Prieska district and the adjoining Carnarvon district, between Copperton and Vanwyksvlei. The fledgling swarms had evidently escaped control over the December period and then coalesced into large swarms before migrating in early January in an easterly direction to invade the Britstown, Hopetown, Philipstown and Hay (Griekwastad) districts. The peak of the control campaign was against the 2nd generation hoppers from mid-January into late March 1978 when a total of 47 control teams were in action in the eight magisterial districts. However, the late summer and autumn of 1978 were very dry due to the El Niño climatic event across the Karoo, which largely halted further breeding through autumn. During March and up until the end of April 1978, the control campaign focused on the tracking down and control of the remaining adult swarms produced by the 2nd generation. A total of 10 435 hopper bands and 1 874 adult swarms were controlled during the 1977/78 season, using a total of 92 250kg of 7% gamma BHC dusting powder. The total cost of the control campaign was given as R131 566.

3.19. 1978/79 season

An intense drought caused by the ongoing El Niño climatic event was occurring across the Karoo. No locust outbreaks were reported, and no control operations took place during the 1978/79 season. There are no records available of any observations of the status of the solitary locust populations in the field.

3.20. 1979/1980 season

Drought conditions continued throughout the Karoo, although comparatively high numbers of solitary phase brown locust adults were reported on a farm in Vosburg district on 21 November 1979 and subsequent surveys revealed high populations of solitary phase locusts on four farms in the Fraserburg district. The adult populations continued to concentrate in this area and during the late summer of 1980 a total of 132 hopper bands and 40 fledging swarms were controlled in two magisterial districts, using 2 030kg of 7% gamma BHC dust. Locust officers reported a relatively high population of solitary phase locusts over a wide area of the Karoo during autumn 1980 and they forecast that a control campaign would be needed against the next generation of adults at the end of 1980 and into 1981.

3.21. Summary of the brown locust outbreaks from 1960/61 to 1979/80

Outbreaks that occurred during the 20-year period, 1960/61 to 1979/80, are briefly summarized in Table 3, showing the number of hopper bands and adult swarms controlled per season, as well as the arbitrary classification of the size and intensity of the different outbreaks and notes on the relevant field conditions. A brown locust 'plague eruption' was defined when >5 000 adult swarms were controlled in the Karoo during a single outbreak season (Price, 2001).

Table 3. Brown locust outbreak summary information over the 20-year period, 1960/61 to 1979/80

Outbreak season	Number of hopper bands controlled	Number of adult swarms controlled	Classification of outbreak season	Notes on field conditions and control operations
1960/61	0	0	Recession	Increase in solitary 'opbouer' populations observed
1961/62	Scattered	0	Recession	Scattered hopper concentrations on one farm in Jansenville district
1962/63	? (no figures available)	? (no figures available)	Medium-scale outbreak	Widespread incipient outbreak in LS 1963. 23 districts in RSA and 8 districts in S. Namibia = 31 districts.
1963-64	>200 000	>20 000	Plague eruption	Intense control ended at Christmas 1963 and collapse of plague. Widespread drought in LS of 1964.
1964-65	323	0	Small-scale outbreak	Initial hatching from egg beds, but population then collapsed
1965-66	0	0	Recession	Suitable for incipient populations
1966-67	13 129	6 412	Widespread incipient outbreak developed to plague status due to the number of swarms	Outbreak rapidly reached plague status in LS of 1967. Control campaign was caught off-guard and was late to combat swarms.
1967-68	>90 000	>3 000	Large-scale outbreak. Very intense in the Free State, eastern Karoo	Late summer drought in 1968 prevented further breeding and stopped large plague developing
1968-69	1 014	18	Incipient concentrations	Dry summer conditions in the Karoo
1969-70	3 646	377	Build-up of incipient populations	Summer 1970 was favorable for locust population build-up and small-scale outbreak developed
1970-71	>250 000	>30 000	Plague (largest since 1950/51)	Rapid eruption in ES of 1970. Locust control organization became overwhelmed. >70 districts infested across the Karoo and beyond.
1971-72	186 005	5 214	Plague continued	Early hatching from egg beds. Vigorous and successful control campaign in 64 districts.
1972-73	Small-scale hopper control in 4 districts only	0	Dormant Season	Relatively dry season. The anticipated continuation of the plague did not materialize. Egg beds in soil?

1973-74	151 437	35 203	Plague eruption	Plague returned with vengeance. Wet season in the Karoo. Control campaign was overwhelmed, with >51 districts infested.
1974-75	168 406	5 460	Plague continued	Early hatching from egg beds. Control campaigns over >31 districts were well organized and effective.
1975-76	18 627	3 659	Medium-scale incipient outbreak	The plague collapsed and no outbreaks occurred before January 1976. Incipient populations developed in late summer 1976.
1976-77	18 980	1 344	Widespread, medium-scale gregarious outbreak	Intense hopper control campaign in spring and early summer 1976 effectively stopped outbreak.
1977-78	10 435	1 874	Medium-scale gregarious outbreak	Intense early outbreak, but drought El Nino during summer of 1978.
1978-79	0	0	Recession	Intense drought conditions across the Karoo and no outbreaks
1979-80	132	40	Small-scale incipient outbreak	Loose concentrations of solitaria 'opbouer' locusts were difficult to control.

Note: ES = Early season (spring and early summer); LS = Late season (late summer, autumn and into winter)

4. Annual rainfall records for the sub-regions of the outbreak area for the period 1980/81 to 2003/04

Following the same rainfall classification index devised by Lea (1969), the rainfall records for RSA Weather Bureau rainfall stations within each of the five geographical sub-regions of the locust outbreak area for the 23-year period, 1980/81 to 2003/2004, were consolidated and averaged for each sub-region for each six-month ES period (July-December), followed by the six-month LS period (January-June) of the following year. A total of 36 rainfall stations across the Karoo were utilized for the study. The mean rainfall total for stations within each separate sub-region were then categorized and colour-coded according to the ES and LS rainfall total classification index given in Table 1 (see materials and methods), namely 'very dry', 'dry', 'normal', 'wet' and 'very wet' for each season from 1980/81 until 2003/04 (Table 4). This classification index of mean rainfall totals gave a good representation of the general rainfall conditions experienced in the different sub-regions, but it was noted that the totals for some individual rainfall stations were sometimes very variable even within the same sub-region due to the scattered rainfall patterns typical of the semi-arid Karoo. The low and variable rainfall conditions, especially during the spring and early summer period, are typical for the Karoo during most years.

The widespread drought conditions experienced in the brown locust outbreak area during many of the study years, as clearly indicated by the yellow and red colour classification

defining the dry and very-dry 6-month periods, were especially prevalent in the western and central sub-regions during both the ES and LS seasons. The western and central sub-regions are known to contain the prime high-frequency outbreaks areas for the brown locust which drive the development of the plague cycles, so favourable rainfall conditions in these areas is critical for the population outbreak dynamics of the brown locust.

Analysis of the mean rainfall received across the western and central sub-regions showed that droughts (dry and very-dry classification), were very common. In fact, the western sub-region experienced 'drought' conditions in >60% of the ES periods and in >80% of the LS periods during the 23-year rainfall study (Table 4). Extended droughts of at least of two-three years were common in the western sub-region. Under the current rainfall classification index, late season (LS) droughts were particularly common throughout the Karoo, as for example between 1981/82 until 1986/87 and then between 1991/92 until 1995/96 (Table 4). However, the rainfall across the Karoo varied greatly during some seasons, with some of the sub-regions being classified as being dry while other sub-regions experienced wet conditions.

4.1. Incidence of El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) events

The El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) describes the conditions of sea surface temperature and thermocline/warm water depth across a vast area of the tropical eastern Pacific Ocean. Fluctuations in the water temperature are driven by a range of regional and global weather patterns and ocean currents, resulting in ocean-atmosphere interactions that then can have a global impact on weather systems. ENSO tends to oscillate seasonally between an El Niño and the La Niña state, with the intensity and timing of the oscillations being difficult to predict. In southern Africa a strong El Niño state is associated with warmer and drier summer seasons (relative to long term averages) in summer rainfall regions, whereas a strong La Niña state is generally associated with cooler and wetter summer seasons. Some of South Africa's worst droughts have been associated with El Niño and some of the worst flooding has been associated with La Niña events. As the dynamic ENSO system is in constant transition, sustained neutral conditions (i.e. classified as in neither an El Niño nor a La Niña state) are rare. However, for the purpose of this study the occurrence of 'weak' El Niño or La Niña conditions that had no discernible impact on the local climate in South Africa were categorised as being a 'neutral' ENSO situation (Ibebuchi, 2021).

The incidence of the El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) events in South Africa (Ibebuchi, 2021) was then highlighted below each of the ES and LS rainfall seasons over the study period (Table 4). Seasons dominated by strong and very strong El Niño drought conditions are shown with a red bar colour, the La Niña wet season events are shown with a blue bar, and 'neutral' events are shown with a green bar. The possible correlation between the various El Niño and La Niña events and some of the intense droughts or unusually wet conditions in the Karoo can be clearly seen (Table 4).

5. Results: Part 2 (Analysis of brown locust outbreaks, 1980/81 to 1994/95)

The annual brown locust outbreaks are described with reference to mean early season and late season rainfall conditions for the 15-year period, 1980/81 to 1994/95. Detailed hand-drawn maps of each of the annual outbreaks (based on the localities of control action undertaken by the DoA locust officers) were electronically scanned for inclusion in this publication and are given where available, along with analysis of the outbreak patterns observed during the early season (ES) and late season (LS) of each outbreak year. Numbers of hopper bands and adult swarms controlled per outbreak season are given.

5.1. 1980/81 season

The early season (ES) rainfall conditions for July-December 1980 were dry in the western and northern sub-regions, with more normal rainfall received in the central and southern sub-regions. However, the eastern sub-region received heavy thundershowers and conditions were considered to be very wet for that time of year. Despite the good rainfall in the eastern Karoo, the anticipated locust outbreak did not develop. The western sub-region continued to remain very dry throughout the late season (LS) January-June period of 1981 and the serious drought that was initiated by the El Niño climatic event of the late 1970s was evident across Bushmanland. However, the central, northern and southern sub-regions received more normal rainfall during the LS of 1981, while the eastern sub-region was very wet during the LS of 1981. Locust population surveys revealed a sharp increase in solitary populations in 10 magisterial districts in the central and eastern Karoo during the LS of 1981, with isolated hopper bands and adult concentrations being controlled in the Murraysburg district and a few small swarms also controlled in the Beaufort West and Phillipstown districts during March-April 1981. Widespread incipient outbreaks were predicted for the following season.

5.2. 1981/82 season

Heavy rainfall during ES 1981 produced wet conditions in the central and southern sub-regions and very wet conditions in the eastern and northern sub-regions. Some areas of the western sub-region received some spring rain, such as Calvinia and Williston, but the rainfall was patchy and large areas of Bushmanland remained under drought conditions. As expected, large-scale incipient hopper outbreaks developed in the central, eastern and southern sub-regions. The chemical control campaign commenced on 5 October 1981 in the Phillipstown district and was followed by control operations from 19 October in the Aberdeen and Beaufort West districts. By end-October the campaign had expanded to a total of 18 magisterial districts, mainly in the eastern, central and southern sub-regions. Only one locust generation developed during the ES of 1981 and the control campaign ended on 16 December 1981. A total of 10 029 hopper bands and 707 adult swarms were controlled by 46 control teams, using a total of 47 297kg of HCH and gamma BHC dusting powder. Intense drought conditions returned across the entire Karoo throughout the LS of 1981/1982, with the western sub-region being very dry and the rest of the Karoo classified as dry, so no further outbreaks developed.

5.3. 1982/83 season

Under the very strong El Niño event of 1982/83, the ES of 1982 remained very dry over most of the western sub-region, but rainfall was more normal in the central, northern and southern sub-regions, and was considered wet in the eastern sub-region. However, no outbreaks were reported. As the El Niño intensified, a serious drought produced dry to very dry conditions over the entire outbreak region during LS 1983, especially in the western sub-region, and no locust outbreaks were reported during the entire 1982/83 season. During a locust survey of the central Karoo and Bushmanland undertaken by PPRI locust researchers during February 1983, no locusts were observed during flush transect counts at any of the sites visited, apart from a few isolated brown locust adults (solitary phase) recorded at one site to the southwest of Pofadder. The locust population was therefore in extreme recession.

5.4. 1983/84 season

Rainfall conditions during ES of 1983 were patchy across most of the western sub-region, with some areas such as Brandvlei, Calvinia and Carnarvon receiving winter rainfall, while towns such as Pofadder remained dry and received <25mm throughout the entire ES of 1983. Rainfall conditions across the rest of the Karoo for the ES of 1983 were generally wet, with widespread good rains experienced across the central and eastern sub-regions. There were reports of isolated “butterfly” concentrations of adult locusts, but no control was undertaken. However, the drought conditions returned under the ongoing El Niño event and the LS of 1984 was very dry over the entire Karoo. Isolated showers enabled a small incipient outbreak to develop in three magisterial Districts (Fauresmith (Luckhoff), Herbert (Douglas) and Philipstown (Petrusville)) during April-May 1984, where 61 hopper bands and 34 fledgling swarms were controlled, using five control teams.

5.5. 1984/85 season (Fig.3)

The ES of 1984 was exceptionally dry in the western sub-region with most rainfall stations recording <20mm rainfall from July-December 1984. However, the rainfall for ES of 1984 was normal to dry across most of the rest of the Karoo, but the ES 1984 was very wet again in the eastern sub-region. Locust concentrations were reported during November 1984 near Koffiefontein in the eastern sub-region, but no reports were received from other areas. The LS of 1985 continued to be very dry in the western sub-region and became dry over the rest of the Karoo. However, a widespread incipient outbreak developed during March-April 1985, and control was required in a total of 11 magisterial districts, with five districts in the central sub-region (Britstown, Carnarvon, Hopetown, Prieska and Victoria West), as well as in five districts in the eastern sub-region (Boshoff, Fauresmith (Luckhoff), Kimberley, Koffiefontein and Petrusburg). A small outbreak was also controlled near Calvinia in the western sub-region. Control was mainly focused in the Victoria West (Vosburg), Carnarvon and Britstown areas, but many locust populations were too scattered for effective control to be undertaken. Up to 10 control teams, using BHC dusters, were employed and the campaign finished in early May. A total of 633 hopper bands and 65 adult swarms/concentrations were controlled during the period November 1984 until the end of March 1985. Control figures for April-May 1985 are not available in the literature. A small-scale hopper outbreak was also controlled in southern Namibia during February-April 1985.

Fig.3. 1984/85 brown locust outbreak.

5.6. 1985/86 season (Fig.4)

Heavy rainfall, as a consequence of an upper troposphere weather system (known as a 'cut-off low' system), fell over the central parts of South Africa during mid-October 1985. The Kalahari region also received heavy rainfalls. Most stations in the central and eastern Karoo received >80mm during October, although the western areas remained dry. Excellent follow-up rains fell during November and December 1985 over the entire Karoo and all sub-regions were classified as being wet to very wet during ES 1985.

The locust outbreak began in October 1985 with massive hopper outbreaks reported in the central Karoo (Britstown, Carnarvon, Victoria west (Vosburg) and Hopetown districts) with slightly later reports from Koffiefontein and Petrusburg in the east. However, the control response was slow and only four control teams were active by the end of October. The control campaign mounted by the South African Department of Agriculture was in chaos and was overpowered by the extent of the outbreak at this time as there was evidently a shortage of Government vehicles and manpower, with temporary locust officers having to be urgently appointed, equipped and trained. From mid-November the outbreak expanded rapidly with hopper bands reported from 16 magisterial districts. An intense outbreak also occurred south of Karasburg in southern Namibia during Nov–Dec 1985. The main centre of the outbreak was in the Carnarvon, Vosburg, Prieska, Van wyksvlei, Britstown area. The Department of Agriculture's spray helicopter (Bell Jet Ranger Mark 2), equipped with 2 x AU4000 atomizers and a UL fenitrothion formulation, was dispatched to the Copperton and Van Wyksvlei areas of the Carnarvon district, where the pilot reported that he sprayed

dozens of large-sized, gregarious hopper bands during November-December 1985 (Paul Davis (DoA helicopter pilot), *pers. comm.*). During December 1985 large swarms developed which began to migrate in all directions. By mid-December a total of 57 control teams were active and the control campaign started to reach public attention with articles in newspapers and on the TV news.

However, soil moisture conditions remained damp from the heavy December 1985 rainfall across the Karoo and swarms laid eggs with the 2nd generation of hoppers appearing during mid-January 1986. The outbreak over a wide area of the Karoo was now out of control as the upsurge gained momentum and developed into a plague. By the end of January 1986, a total of 145 control teams were active, with 6-13 teams active in each of the worst infested districts of Carnarvon, Prieska, Victoria West (Vosburg) and Richmond. The DoA helicopter and a fix-wing spray aircraft were also deployed in the Carnarvon district. Urgent appeals for the release of extra funds were made to central Government.

By mid-February 1986, thousands of gregarious hopper bands were present over much of the Upper and Central Karoo and there was a strong northerly movement of hundreds of loose swarms right up to the Molopo border with Botswana. A 2nd generation of hoppers also developed as a separate outbreak in the Warmbad and Karasburg districts in southern Namibia during Feb-March 1986 with swarms reported to migrate in a north-westerly direction into the Mariental and Maltahohe districts by April. Adult swarms also developed in the Great Karoo in the southern sub-region and throughout the eastern sub-region and huge swarms were reported to have blocked out the sun as they flew for hours over the town of Graaf-Reinet in the Eastern Province. At least 350 control teams were now deployed and the SA army also provided assistance with 50 additional vehicles and drivers. During early March 1986, numerous large swarms slowly migrated north and northwest invading the Gordonia, Postmasburg, Kuruman and Vryburg districts before crossing the Botswana border and disappearing into the Central Kalahari Desert. Swarms were later reported to have reached as far north as 21°N in Botswana. Swarms were also reported invading the city of Kimberley and the maize producing areas of Schweizer-Reneke and Christiana where crop damage was sustained. Damage to maize crops was also reported from various areas along the Orange River valley.

The LS 1986 rainfall was very dry in the western and central sub-divisions of the Karoo and dry in the other areas. The control campaign peaked during late March 1986 when up to 458 ground control teams were in operation in 55 magisterial districts, as well as 1 helicopter and 5 spray aircraft. Large swarms had invaded the Eastern Province and threatened agriculture at Cradock and Somerset East. New hatchings of the 3rd generation occurred in Kenhardt (Pofadder), Frazerburg, Hay (Griquatown), Herbert (Douglas) and Barkley West. New hatchings also occurred in the northern districts of Postmasburg, Vryburg and Kuruman where swarms had laid eggs as they migrated northwards into Botswana. By mid-April the control campaign had greatly subsided under the prevailing dry field conditions and had virtually come to an end during early May 1986. A total of >175 000 hopper bands and >40 000 adult swarms were controlled in South Africa between October 1985 and May 1986. Approximately 5 803 tonnes of BHC dusting powder (7% gamma isomer) were applied during the 1985/86 outbreak in the Karoo, along with approximately 535 000 litres of organophosphate insecticide, comprising 182 tonnes (active ingredient) of UL diazinon and fenitrothion, and 32 tonnes (active ingredient) of EC diazinon formulation (Brown, 1988). The cost of control was estimated at R48 million in South Africa, along with approximately R500 000 in southern Namibia and Pula 1.5 million in Botswana. At its peak in March 1986 the locust upsurge covered an area of over 1 million km², infesting at least 88 magisterial

districts in south Africa, Namibia and Botswana, was considered the worst brown locust plague recorded for over 60 years.

Fig.4. 1985/86 brown locust outbreak.

However, the 1985/86 upsurge was not entirely finished as the numerous swarms that had invaded Botswana during February and March 1986 successfully bred deep in the remote central Kalahari region, where warm autumn and winter temperatures enabled a further generation to be produced. Gregarious 5th instar hopper bands were reported in the Kutze Game Reserve in late April (Lesley Henderson, PPRI botanist, *pers. comm.*). A large-scale aerial spray campaign was undertaken against roosting as well as flying swarms in eastern and southern Botswana as they flew out of the Central Kalahari. However, migrating brown locust swarms continued to invade South Africa from Botswana during winter 1986 up until the end of September 1986 (Fig.5). The swarms were controlled by spray aircraft in various places in the Free State and North West Provinces, such as at Potchefstroom, Koppies, Ventersdorp and Bothaville, mainly applying UL organophosphate insecticides (fenitrothion and diazinon). However, a number of swarms evaded control and eventually made their way back into the eastern and central Karoo, thereby completing the classic return migrations from the Kalahari Desert which were last observed during the brown locust plague cycles of the 1920s (Lea, 1958). Some of these swarms undoubtedly laid eggs before being controlled.

Fig.5. Brown locust swarm migrations in winter 1986

5.7. 1986/87 season (Fig.6)

The ES 1986 continued to be very dry in the western and central sub-regions under the strong El Niño conditions, while normal to wet conditions prevailed in the south and east. The first hatchings were observed by ARC-PPRI researchers in early September in the Vryburg district in the northern sub-region, where hatching occurred from extensive egg beds that had been laid by migrating swarms the previous autumn. Some egg beds measured over 3km² in extent, with pod densities of >500 pods/m² found in selected quadrats. Hatching hoppers produced dense bands that stretched over hundreds of meters in length. Widespread hatching from overwintering egg beds was reported during September–October from many areas in the northern, eastern and southern sub-regions. However, only isolated outbreaks occurred in the central and western sub-regions due to the very dry conditions prevailing in these areas which restricted hatching. Scattered outbreaks were also reported in southern Namibia and southern Botswana during September–January.

After the harsh lessons learnt from the previous season's massive control campaign, the DoA was well prepared and the ES 1986 campaign got off to a vigorous start, with insecticide stores strategically positioned and locust officers employed and ready for action. The control campaign expanded rapidly with 62 magisterial districts infested with hopper

bands by mid-October, and up to a maximum of 304 control teams employed at a time. The DoA spray helicopter was used to control hopper bands in the mountainous areas of the Middleburg and Graaff-Reinet districts, but no fixed-spray aircraft were required. The dry field conditions also tended to concentrate the hopper bands into large targets. The effective and well-organised control campaign against the 1st generation hopper outbreak was a great success with approximately 63,000 hopper bands and 400 adult swarms controlled up until the end of December 1986, which ensured that the great 1985/86 plague cycle came to an end.

2nd generation

The LS 1987 was dry to very-dry over the entire Karoo and the anticipated widespread 2nd generation of hoppers failed to materialize. However, scattered rain showers in mid-February enabled small-scale incipient outbreaks to develop in the central and eastern sub-regions during February-March 1987 (Fig.8) when 30 control teams were active in 17 magisterial districts and controlled approximately 6 000 hopper bands and 1 400 swarms. Therefore, during the 1986/87 locust season a total of 68,896 hopper bands and 1,803 adult swarms were controlled using 768,525kg of HCH and gamma BHC dust and 105,600 liters of UL formulation (organophosphates: fenitrothion, diazinon, and the synthetic pyrethroid insecticide, fenvalerate).

Fig.6. 1986/87 brown locust outbreak.

5.8. 1987/88 season (Fig.7)

The ES of 1987 was dry in the western sub-region, but very wet in the central and eastern sub-regions. Despite the high rainfall conditions, only scattered outbreaks occurred in the central, eastern and northern sub-regions during October 1987. The outbreak was most intense in the Hanover and De Aar districts in the central sub-region where most hopper bands were quickly and effectively controlled in the L1 and L2 instar stage. Very isolated outbreaks also occurred in the Williston district and in southern Namibia (Karasburg). Good follow-up rains fell in many areas, and the rainfall of LS of 1988 was considered to be normal/wet to very wet throughout the Karoo. However, locust populations remained surprisingly low and widespread outbreaks were not expected.

2nd generation

A small-scale 2nd generation outbreak later developed in February-May 1988, especially in the Hopetown, Britstown and Phillipstown districts in the central sub-region where the control effort was mainly directed against adult swarms. Scattered locust populations were reported in many areas of the central and eastern sub-regions. Isolated outbreaks also developed near the towns of Marydale and Pofadder in the western sub-region, and also in southern

Namibia where 1,050 hopper bands and 15 swarms were controlled on 13 farms in the southern Warmbad district.

A total of 5,618 hopper bands and 1,123 adult swarms were controlled in the Karoo using 11,000kg of BHC dust, 9,192 liters water-emulsifiable concentrate (EC fenvalerate) and 14,368 liters of UL formulation oil-based insecticides. Up to 41 control teams were active. The high ratio of the number of swarms compared to bands controlled, especially in the LS of 1988, suggested that the campaign had started too late and that many swarms had escaped and had laid eggs.

Fig.7. 1987/88 brown locust outbreak.

5.9. 1988/89 season (Fig.8)

Following on from the high summer rainfall, the ES 1988 continued to be very wet in the central and eastern sub-regions and normal in the west. First hatchings were reported on 20 September 1988 near Gamoep in the western sub-region and were soon followed by scattered outbreaks in other parts of the western, central and eastern sub-regions. The most intense campaign was fought in the De Aar, Britstown and Hopetown districts with 10 control teams active in each district. By mid-November 1988 a total of 58 control teams and the DoA spray helicopter were active in 16 magisterial districts. The campaign against the 1st generation closed in late December. Scattered small-scale outbreaks were reported in

southern Namibia, along the edge of the Namib desert to the west of Maltahohe and southwest of Helmeringhausen. A small outbreak was also reported from Kang in Botswana.

2nd generation

The good rains that fell in December 1988 led to successful breeding over the Christmas period and a large-scale 2nd generation developed in the western sub-region during early January 1989. The outbreak was particularly intense in the Gamoep-Pofadder-Marydale area, and good follow-up rains in early February 1989 favored survival of the population. The population fledged during mid-February and adult swarms were observed during an ARC-PPRI survey in the Gamoep and Pofadder areas, while over 600 medium- to large-size adult swarms were controlled in the Kenhardt and Carnarvon districts during February 1989. Other swarms escaped from the above areas and flew north across the Orange River to invade the Groblershoop and Kakamas areas in Gordonia district, where they laid eggs. An intense hopper campaign was waged in these areas until late March. Widespread hopper outbreaks were also combatted in the Britstown, Strydenburg, Hopetown, and Victoria West districts in the central sub-region during January–February. A small 2nd generation outbreak was also reported near Beaufort West in the Great Karoo of the southern sub-region and also from a few farms in southern Namibia.

3rd generation

A widespread 3rd generation of hoppers erupted in late February–March 1989 across the entire Northern Cape Province from Springbok to Prieska. The outbreak was most intense in the Pofadder, Brandvlei, Van Wyksvlei and Marydale areas with up to 145 control teams in action. Despite the intense control effort, thousands of swarms came onto the wing and began to migrate. Towards the end of March 1989, strong north-westerly winds blew swarms from Bushmanland and the Upper Karoo in a southerly and south-easterly direction to invade the districts of Fraserburg, Murraysburg, Beaufort West, Victoria West, Laingsburg, Prince Albert and even Oudtshoorn.

During April, numerous large-size adult swarms migrated east and invaded the Britstown and Hopetown districts. Two spray aircraft were employed in the Britstown area to combat these swarms, while the DoA spray helicopter-controlled swarms in the Van Wyksvlei and Victoria West areas. Other swarms flew further southeast and invaded the Graaff-Reinet and Aberdeen districts. Numerous fledgling swarms were present all over the western and central sub-regions, and >2 000 adult swarms were controlled each week from mid-March to mid-April, with over half of the targets described as being large-size. Over the next month, hundreds of maturing swarms continued to migrate south and southeast and invaded the Murraysburg, Beaufort West, Sutherland, Prince Albert, Aberdeen and Willowmore districts during April–May. Many swarms were reported to be mature and locust officers reported egg beds being deposited by the swarms in some of these areas.

4th generation

From late April new hatchings of a 4th generation were reported in the Pofadder, Gamoep, Kenhardt and Loriesfontein areas of the western sub-region. The hopper control campaign continued until mid-June in these areas despite the winter conditions. The hopper campaign was successful, and most hoppers were controlled before they could fledge into adults. One small hopper band was also controlled during mid-May in the Aberdeen district - probably the progeny of one of the migrating swarms.

Fig.8. 1988/89 brown locust outbreak.

The serious brown locust upsurge of the 1988/89 season reached plague proportions and only came to a close in July 1989. A total of 85 935 hopper bands and 12 642 adult swarms were controlled in South Africa in 34 magisterial districts using 810 000kg of BHC dust and 390 000 liters of UL insecticides. Due to the number of egg beds reported, a widespread hopper campaign was anticipated for the next spring, especially in the southern sub-region.

5.10. 1989/90 season (Fig.9)

The ES of 1989 was very dry in the west and north, dry in the central sub-region and normal in the east and south. The first hatchings were reported on 11 September 1989 and scattered outbreaks developed during September in the Calvinia, Loeriesfontein, Kliprand and Gamoep areas in the western sub-region, and at Aberdeen in the south. As anticipated, an intense outbreak developed during October-November in the southern sub-region where better rains had fallen with 12 districts being infested, especially the Beaufort West, Aberdeen and Murraysburg districts. The hopper campaign got out of hand in the Beaufort West district during November where 15-21 control teams controlled up to 3 000 hopper bands per week. A less intense outbreak also developed in the Victoria West and Britstown

districts in the central sub-region, and in the Carnarvon-Van Wyksvlei area in the west. A total of over 31 000 hopper bands were controlled in the Karoo between September and mid December 1989. No outbreaks were reported from Namibia or Botswana.

The first adult swarms came onto the wing in late November and by early December 1989 more than 300 swarms were being controlled per week in the Beaufort West district alone. Hundreds of fledgling swarms evidently escaped control, and from 15 December these were blown in a north and north-easterly direction on strong southwesterly winds associated with the passage of a cold weather front. The immature swarms flew hundreds of kilometers and invaded all the central and eastern Karoo, as well as the western half of the Free State Province. On 19-20 December a strong westerly wind drove the migrating swarms eastwards and some flew over the Provincial capitals of Kimberley and Bloemfontein and even invaded the western half of Lesotho on Christmas Eve. A widespread campaign against these migrating swarms was mounted, with nearly 1 400 swarms being controlled by early January 1990. The sight of migrating swarms escaping from their traditional Karoo outbreak area caused much excitement in the media.

2nd generation

The LS of 1990 remained fairly dry in the west, but more normal rainfall fell in the central and eastern sub-regions. The exodus of migrating swarms from the southern and central Karoo in late December effectively cleared these sub-regions of gregarious locust populations. Apart from small-scale outbreaks near Britstown, Belmont and Douglas in February-March, a widespread 2nd generation failed to materialize in the central and eastern Karoo. However, an intense 2nd generation outbreak developed in the Pofadder and Gamoep area in the western sub-region during February 1990, as well as isolated outbreaks in the Loeriesfontein, Sutherland and Williston areas. The hopper control campaign came to a successful end in early May 1990 before hardly any swarms could develop. A small outbreak also developed in the Maltahohe and Luderitz districts in southern Namibia during February 1990 where 279 hopper bands and 9 swarms were controlled.

The 1989/90 locust outbreak was characterized by the intense 1st generation of hoppers in the southern sub-region and by numerous immature swarms escaping from the Karoo during December. A total of 36 553 hopper bands and 1 392 swarms were controlled during the season in 46 magisterial districts. Swarms also invaded an additional 4 districts outside the Karoo, and invaded Lesotho. A total of 101 166kg of BHC dusting powder and 53 746 liters of UL formulated insecticides were applied.

Fig.9. 1989/90 brown locust outbreak.

5.11. 1990/91 season (Fig.10)

The ES of 1990 was very dry over almost the entire Karoo and the only locust activity reported was a small-scale incipient outbreak reported in late December 1990 near Belmont in the Herbert district, and on a few farms in the Jacobsdal district. Approximately 77 hopper bands and 32 adult swarms were controlled by mid-January 1991. The drought in the central, eastern and northern Karoo was broken by good rains in January 1991, and these sub-regions remained wet to very wet throughout LS 1991. However, the western and southern sub-regions remain dry.

A 2nd generation developed in the Herbert and Jacobsdal districts in February 1991 and the outbreak expanded to include parts of the Fauresmith (Luckhoff) and Koffiefontein districts. The first isolated outbreaks of the season were reported in the Hopetown and Hay (Griekwastad) districts during February-March 1991, and a few bands were reported hatching from egg beds located near Gamoep in the western sub-region. The 1990/91 season produced a small-scale outbreak and only 1 142 hopper bands and 357 adult swarms required control. However, during February 1991, the solitaria phase adult locusts were regularly observed being attracted to lights at night at towns in the central Karoo, suggesting that solitary populations were building up in this area.

Fig.10. 1990/91 brown locust outbreak.

5.12. 1991/92 season (Fig.11)

Rainfall during the ES of 1991 was normal in the western and southern sub-regions and very wet in the central, northern and eastern sub-regions. The first hatchings were reported on 12 October 1991 in the Jacobsdal district. By mid-November 1991 incipient outbreaks were being combated from a number of areas scattered over the eastern, central, southern and western sub-regions. The most intense hopper campaign was fought in the Beaufort West, Williston, Victoria West and Hopetown districts. However, only 1-2 control teams were employed in each district at any one time. The first adult swarms came onto the wing in mid-November. During early December at least 100 swarms escaped from the Beaufort West area and flew in an easterly direction to invade the Murraysburg, Aberdeen and Jansenville districts. A number of swarms also escaped control in most of the other infested districts. Good rain fell over a wide area in December 1991 and swarms laid eggs.

2nd generation

A widespread 2nd generation developed in early January 1992 throughout the southern and central sub-regions and at Carnarvon-Van Wyksvlei in the western sub-region. The hopper control campaign was most intense in the Aberdeen, Beaufort West, Jansenville and Murraysburg districts in the southern sub-region, with 8-10 control teams active in each district. Hoppers were even controlled in the Pearston and Willowmore districts. The first swarms came onto the wing at the end of January and over 1 000 swarms were controlled

during February, especially in the Aberdeen and Beaufort West districts. Towards the end of February 1992, the immature swarms started to migrate and there was a strong displacement of swarms in a northeasterly and easterly direction. Some of the large swarms were observed to fly at least 100-120km per day. In early March, swarms invaded the southern Free State Province and had flown to the north of Kimberley. However, under the prevailing strong El Niño 1991/92 season, the LS of 1992 was very dry throughout the entire Karoo and there was insufficient green grass available for the swarms to mature eggs, and they quickly flew away from their fledging areas. The evacuation of immature swarms from dry areas is characteristic of the brown locust.

3rd generation

The prevailing dry conditions caused the outbreak to largely die out, although there was a localised 3rd generation of hoppers in the Beaufort West, Aberdeen, Graaf-Reinet, Jansenville and Steylerville areas of the southern sub-region during March 1992. A very small outbreak was also controlled in the Carnarvon district in late April. The campaign came to an end in early May.

The 1991/92 outbreak was characterised by the relatively inefficient hopper control campaign against the 1st generation in the southern sub-region, which allowed swarms to escape and lay eggs. A widespread 2nd generation then developed, and hundreds of swarms migrated out of the Karoo, but under the prevailing dry conditions very few swarms had time to mature and to lay eggs before being controlled. A total of 18 131 hopper bands and 1 603 adult swarms were controlled in 37 magisterial districts.

Fig.11. 1991/92 brown locust outbreak.

5.13. 1992/93 outbreak season (Fig.12)

The ES of 1992 remained very dry in the western and northern sub-regions and dry to normal in the rest of the Karoo. Scattered showers in August 1992 enabled a small outbreak to develop in parts of the Britstown, De Aar and Hanover districts in the central sub-region during late September and into October 1992. The gregarious hoppers hatched from overwintering egg beds that had been laid by migrating swarms the previous autumn 1992. A total of 72 hopper bands were controlled, mainly in the 1st and 2nd instar stage. No adult swarms developed, but concentrations of sub-swarming adults were reported in various areas of the central sub-region (Britstown, Hopetown, De Aar and Philipstown districts). The western sub-region of the Karoo was experiencing an intense drought and the LS of 1993 continued to be very-dry to dry over the entire Karoo. No further outbreaks were reported.

Fig.12. 1992/93 brown locust outbreak.

5.14. 1993/94 season (Fig.13)

Improved rainfall conditions returned to most of the Karoo, and the ES of 1993 was normal in the central and southern sub-regions and very wet in the east. However, conditions in the western sub-region remained quite dry until heavy rain fell in January 1994. Isolated incipient hopper outbreaks were first controlled during the third week of November 1993 near Griekwastad in the Hay district (northern sub-region) and in the Petrusburg and Phillipolis districts in the eastern Karoo. However, concentrations of solitary and transient phase hoppers and fledgling adults were reported during December from a wide area across the central, western and northern sub-regions, with locust officers raising concern that they were

not sufficiently aggregated to form sprayable targets. Isolated hopper concentrations (total of 64 control actions) were controlled in the Prieska, Williston, Hay, and Brandfort districts during December 1993, with five fledgling concentrations also controlled near Petrusburg.

2nd generation

Good rainfall fell over most of the Karoo during December-January and a widespread incipient outbreak developed during January-February 1994 in the northern, central and eastern sub-regions. The outbreak was particularly intense in the Hopetown, Hanover, Philippolis and Koffiefontein districts. The large-scale outbreak intensified during the first two weeks of February with nearly 2 000 hopper bands controlled across the central, eastern and northeastern part of the outbreak area, particularly in the Koffiefontein, Hopetown, Hanover and Kuruman districts. The first adult swarms came onto the wing from mid-February, and the hopper campaign intensified across a wide area. Of interest was the intense outbreak in the southern Kalahari (savanna thorn-veld) straddling the border between South Africa and southern Botswana, with hundreds of hopper bands and at least 80 swarms controlled in the Gordonia, Kuruman and Hay districts during February. Widespread outbreaks were also reported in February 1994 from the Karasburg district and from various localities near Keetmashoop in southern Namibia. Isolated hopper outbreaks were also controlled during late February in the Pofadder and Marydale areas of the western sub-region. Control teams were also active in the Pofadder, Brandvlei and Williston areas controlling adult swarms that were migrating south-west from the intense outbreaks being combated in the Kuruman, Gordonia and Prieska districts. Swarms also flew south-east from the central Karoo (Hanover) and invaded the Middelburg, Hofmeyr and Cradock districts in the eastern sub-region during late February.

3rd generation

The rainfall of LS 1994 was dry to normal over most of the Karoo, but wet in the eastern sub-region, and a third generation developed over a wide area across the western, central and northern sub-regions during March-April 1994. The outbreak was very severe in the Carnarvon-VanWyksvlei, Marydale, Prieska, Groblershoop, Kenhardt, Kakamas and Pofadder areas, with thousands of hopper bands and hundreds of adult swarms were controlled each week. The outbreak in the Kalahari veld of the Gordonia district continued with >2 800 hopper bands controlled there during the first three weeks of March. An intense hopper and adult control campaign was also undertaken in the Brandvlei and Calvinia areas, which was the progeny of swarms that had invaded the area during February. A total of 12,003 bands and 768 swarms were controlled in March 1994.

Hundreds of adult swarms came onto the wing from mid-March, and by mid-April the campaign became focused on swarm control over a wide area of the Upper Central Karoo and the western sub-region (Bushmanland) with approximately 200 ground control teams in action. The most intense control operations took place in the Carnarvon, Britstown, Prieska and Victoria West districts in the Upper Central Karoo, in the Calvinia-Williston-Brandvlei area and across Bushmanland in the Kenhardt and Namaqualand districts in the western sub-region, and also in the Gordonia district in the Kalahari veld of the northern sub-region. A total of >20 000 hopper bands and >4 000 adults swarms were controlled during the month of April. Locust officers also reported vast areas occupied by incipient transient phase locusts at too low a density to control. An outbreak was also reported in southern Namibia during March-April 1994.

From mid-April, hundreds of immature adult swarms migrated in an easterly and southeasterly direction on the prevailing northwesterly winds and invaded the Hopetown, De

Aar, Hanover, Philipstown and Richmond districts. Swarms in the western Bushmanland area flew northwest into the Springbok area in Namaqualand. During the first two weeks of May a significant number of large swarms (± 500) continued to fly south and southeast into the Murraysburg, Beaufort West, Willowmore, Prince Albert, Aberdeen, Graaf-Reinet and Jansenville districts. Other swarms continued to invade the eastern Karoo. A total of 869 hopper bands and 1 016 swarms were controlled in May, with numerous swarms escaping control. During mid-May a PPRI survey dissected samples of locusts collected from migrating swarms in the Aberdeen and Jansenville districts, which proved that locusts were mature and that some swarms were ready to lay eggs. A swarm was, in fact, observed ovipositing in the Aberdeen district on 21 May (Price, *pers. obs.*).

The hopper campaign finally closed in mid-May, although swarms continued to fly southeast into the Jansenville, Willowmore and Somerset East districts of the southern sub-region up until the first week of July. The migrating swarms entering the Great Karoo and the southeastern Karoo throughout May and June laid a substantial number of egg beds before they were controlled. A large-scale hopper campaign throughout the southern sub-region was predicted for spring 1994 following the hatching of overwintering egg beds. Official records show that a total of 37,883 bands and 6,263 swarms were controlled during the 1993/94 season, which was classified as yet another brown locust 'plague' season.

Fig. 13. 1993/94 brown locust outbreak.

5.15. 1994/95 season (Fig. 14)

Under the moderate intensity El Niño event of 1994/95 that impacted the summer rainfall areas, the ES of 1994 was very dry across almost the entire Karoo except for those areas that had received some winter rainfall back in July. The winter rain had ensured that the quiescent eggs lying in the soil had absorbed water and became turgid and were ready to develop to hatching once soil temperatures rose in spring. The first hatchings were reported during the 2nd and 3rd weeks of September from the winter rainfall areas of Van Rhynsdorp, Kliprand, Loeriesfontein (Calvinia) and Gamoep (Namaqualand). Resulting from the winter rain received, scattered hatching was also reported from mid-September in the Beaufort West, Aberdeen and Jansenville districts of the southern sub-region. A small outbreak was also reported in the Britstown district. Despite the large overwintering egg population that was suspected to have been laid by the migrating swarms during early winter 1994 in the southern and eastern Karoo, the dry ES conditions prevented the general hatching of egg beds. The partial hatching of egg beds was observed in the Aberdeen district (Price, *pers. obs.*), probably due to the scenario where the upper eggs in pods near the soil surface had absorbed sufficient moisture to become turgid during the winter rain season, which then proceeded to develop to hatching under the warm September soil temperatures. However, the winter rains had not been sufficient to penetrate deeper into the soil to soak the lower layers of eggs in pods which therefore remained quiescent in the soil awaiting more soaking rains. By mid-October, more hopper bands were being controlled, especially in Calvinia and Beaufort West Districts, with small outbreaks reported over a wide area from Jansenville and Aberdeen in the southeast, to Sutherland in the southwest and Namaqualand in the northwest part of the outbreak area. A total of 1 600 hopper bands had been controlled by mid-October, but only 1-2 control teams were required in each of the infested districts and most of the hopper targets were reported as being of small size.

From mid-October 1994, the hopper control campaign continued to expand in the winter rainfall areas of the western sub-region (Loeriesfontein-Gamoep areas). The control campaign also expanded rapidly in the Great Karoo (southern sub-region) from late October and was most intense in the Beaufort West district where 10 control teams were in action and 2 699 bands were controlled during early November. Vigorous control operations were also underway in the Jansenville, Aberdeen, Willowmore and Prince Albert Districts. The first adult swarms were controlled in the western sub-region during early November. By the end of November 1994, over 80 control teams were in action and the hopper campaign expanded to include large areas of the western, central, southern and eastern Karoo (Fig. 94/95). Adult swarms started to come onto the wing in the south-eastern Karoo (Jansenville) and southern Karoo (Beaufort West) from late November / early December and by the end of December 1994 over 11 500 hopper bands and 140 adult swarms had been controlled in approximately 30 Karoo districts. A control campaign was also fought in the Karasburg district in southern Namibia during November.

2nd generation

In addition to the high populations of solitary phase locusts reported from areas of the western and central Karoo, a number of swarms also escaped control in the southern sub-region during December-January and flew north. Widespread rains in January 1995 allowed a second generation of hoppers to develop and from mid-January 1995 the control campaign became increasingly engaged in the western and central sub-regions (Fig. 14). The Loeriesfontein-Calvinia and Gamoep areas in the western sub-region, and the Victoria West and Richmond districts in the central sub-region were especially active. There was also an intense hopper campaign in the Fraserburg district in January 1995. However, in contrast

with the intense campaign waged against the 1st generation in the Beaufort West, Aberdeen and Jansenville districts, the 2nd generation outbreak in these districts was very feeble, confirming that most of the swarms had flown out of these districts before laying eggs. No 2nd generation outbreak was reported in southern Namibia.

The hopper campaign expanded during February, especially in the Calvinia district (>3000 bands controlled), with heavy infestations also being combated in the Carnarvon (>1 500 bands), Fraserburg (>1 000 bands) and Victoria West district (>1 300 bands). Hopper band control was also undertaken in the Hanover and Prieska districts. The first adult swarms from the 2nd generation came onto the wing from mid-February and started to migrate in various directions. Hundreds of immature swarms were reported and many then started to coalesce to form larger swarm targets. For example, in early March at least 20 large swarms invaded the Britstown district, and 40 swarms invaded the Kakamas district respectively. However, the intense hopper and swarm control campaign being waged across the Karoo, combined with the very dry summer season (LS 1995) in the western sub-region, prevented the outbreak from getting out of control. The hopper campaign ended by mid-March and control then focused on tracking down and mopping up the immature swarms that were migrating around the Karoo. Approximately 11 500 bands and 500 adult swarms were controlled in the second generation.

3rd generation

Isolated hatchings of the third generation appeared in April-May in the Gamoep, Brandvlei, Marydale, Victoria West and Beaufort West areas where just a few small hopper bands required control. The outbreak was more substantial in the Fraserburg district in the southern sub-region where approximately 180 bands were controlled. Control action was successful and only six swarms required control in the Fraserburg district and one swarm in the Gamoep area during mid-May, with the outbreak then coming to an end.

A total of 23 369 hopper bands and 780 adult swarms were controlled during the season. The development of the 1994/95 outbreak was curtailed by the vigorous and wide-spread control action against the 2nd generation, along with the prevailing dry conditions in the western sub-region, resulting in the outbreak petering out before a strong 3rd generation could get going. Whether egg beds were still lying dormant in the western and central sub-regions waiting for adequate rain was unknown.

Fig. 14. 1994/95 brown locust outbreak.

5.16. Summary of the brown locust outbreaks from 1980/81 to 1994/95

A summary of the brown locust outbreak information described for the 15-year period, 1980/81 to 1994/95, as derived from analysis of the hand-drawn outbreak maps, is given in Table 5. The number of hopper bands and adult swarms controlled per season, the classification of the size and intensity of the different outbreaks and notes on the relevant field conditions are provide (Table 5). A brown locust 'plague eruption' season was defined when >5 000 adult swarms were controlled in the Karoo (Price, 2001).

Table 5. Brown locust outbreak summary for the 15-year period, 1980/81 to 1994/95

Outbreak season	Number of hopper bands controlled	Number of adult swarms controlled	Classification of outbreak season	Notes on field conditions and control operations
1980/81	A few scattered bands controlled in Murraysburg	A few adult 'opbouer' concentrations	Small-scale incipient populations	Field conditions are good for locust breeding. Scattered populations observed across 10 districts. Control operations in 3 districts.
1981/82	10 029	707	Large-scale incipient outbreak	Good early rains across eastern and southern Karoo. 18 districts infested. Control ended mid-December 1981. Summer drought in Karoo.

1982/83	0	0	Recession	Drought El Nino conditions across the entire Karoo. Egg banks lying dormant in the soil from previous season?
1983/84	61	34	Scattered concentrations. Small-scale outbreak	Ongoing El Nino drought conditions. Scattered concentrations in 3 eastern districts in LS of 1984.
1984/85	>633	>65	Widespread incipient concentrations. Small-scale outbreak	It remained dry in the western sub-region. Incipient concentrations in 11 districts, mainly in the central and eastern Karoo in late summer 1985.
1985/86	>175 000	>40 000	Large plague (most serious and widespread outbreak since the 1930s)	Heavy ES rains triggered an intense and widespread outbreak. Control peaked in March 1985 with 458 control teams active. Dry LS of 1985 subdued the late autumn outbreak.
1986/87	68 896	1 803	Large-scale outbreak. Ongoing plague from 1985/86 brought under control by December 1986	Widespread gregarious hatching in spring 86. Vigorous and successful control in ES 1986 caused the outbreak to collapse. Dry conditions in LS 1987 prevented further breeding.
1987/88	5 618	1 123	Small-scale outbreak	Intense and successful ES campaign in central sub-region. Small 2 nd generation in LS 1988. Widespread scattered 'opbouer' locusts.
1988/89	85 935	12 642	Plague eruption	Wet conditions and large ES outbreak in central Karoo, followed by intense outbreak in western and central sub-regions. Many migrating swarms flew S and SE.
1989/90	36 553	1 392	Medium-scale outbreak	Intense hopper campaign in ES in southern and central sub-regions. Escaping swarms flew N and NE and exited the Karoo.
1990/91	1 142	357	Small-scale outbreak	Dry ES of 1990, followed by small outbreaks in the eastern sub-region in LS of 1991. Widespread 'opbouer' solitary phase adults also reported in LS 1991.
1991/92	18 131	1 603	Medium-scale outbreak	Incipient outbreak over wide area, but most intense in southern sub-region. Dry LS of 1992 and swarms exited southern Karoo areas.

1992/93	72	0	Small and very localized outbreak from overwintering egg beds	Very dry over most of the Karoo. Small ES outbreaks in 3 districts in central sub-region. LS of 1993 very dry and no further outbreaks.
1993/94	37 887	6 263	Plague eruption	Widespread incipient outbreak rapidly gregarized in summer 1994 across the central, western and northern sub-regions. Intense outbreak in Gordonias Kalahari veld.
1994/95	23 369	780	Medium-scale outbreak	Dry conditions but hatching in ES in winter-rainfall areas from egg beds. Widespread outbreak developed in LS of 1995 in western and central sub-regions.

6. Results: Part 3 (Analysis of brown locust outbreaks, 1995/96 to 2004/05)

6.1. Revised boundaries of the brown locust outbreak area

As discussed earlier, the recognized outbreak area of the brown locust was defined by Lea (1958), based on analysis of the expenditure on locust control in each magisterial district in the Karoo over a 25-year period between 1933–1958, with districts showing a low, medium and high outbreak frequency identified. The boundary line of the ‘saddle-shaped’ outbreak area was therefore used in the hand-drawn outbreak maps generated by PPRI for the period 1984/85 until the 1994/95 season. However, the boundaries of the outbreak area were subsequently redrawn by Kieser, Thackrah & Rosenberg (2002) based on detailed analysis of the distribution and frequency of the first-generation gregarious hatchings of the locust season per magisterial district from 1984 to 2001. It must be noted that gregarious swarming populations often develop in areas outside the boundaries of the ‘recognised outbreak area’, where escaping swarms evade control during the larger-scale upsurges and migrate into the surrounding invasion area and then continue to breed. However, the gregarious outbreaks that occur in locations outside the recognised outbreak area are generally short-term for only a generation or two, so such outbreak records were not considered while delimiting the boundary of the outbreak area.

The revised outbreak area, shown in Fig. 15 below, was therefore used in subsequent outbreak maps from 1995/96 onwards which have been generated digitally using ArcGIS mapping of the ¼ degree square database of farm localities where locust control had been undertaken each season. Annual outbreak maps are provided for the numbers of hopper bands and adult swarms controlled per ¼ degree square.

Fig. 15. The revised outbreak area of the brown locust, adapted from Kieser, Thackrah and Rosenberg (2001). The location of main towns in the Karoo are given for reference.

The revised outbreak area of the brown locust was shown to have moved significantly westward by ± 100 km compared with the previous boundary area defined by Lea (1958) and now occupies the central and western Karoo as far as Calvinia and includes much of Bushmanland in the northwest (Fig. 15). The shift of eastern boundary line further to the west has been so dramatic that the former high-frequency outbreak centre of the Middelburg district in the eastern Karoo (Lea, 1958) has become insignificant as a locust outbreak centre and is now situated outside the revised boundaries. Rainfall is a key driver of ecosystem processes, especially vegetation dynamics in semi-arid regions and this westward shift of the outbreak area was ascribed to changes in rainfall patterns with the eastern Karoo receiving more rainfall that resulted in a higher grass cover (Hoffmann and Cowling, 1990; Du Toit, et al., 2018; Kieser Thackrah and Rosenberg, 2001). A more detailed study of the rainfall patterns in the Middleburg district over a 123-year period showed that annual rainfall during the 30-year period, 1980–2010, was considerably higher (annual mean = 413 mm) than for the preceding 81 years (annual mean = 347 mm; 1899–1980) (Du Toit and O'Connor, 2014). There was strong evidence of climate cycles influencing the rainfall pattern, with a short 20-year rainfall cycle identified, except for spring rain. Additionally, annual and seasonal rainfall showed evidence of a longer cycle over 44–77 years, possibly related to the southern oscillation index (Du Toit and O'Connor, 2014). The wetter rainfall cycles experienced in the eastern Karoo, along with improved veld

management practices and the lower sheep stocking rates enforced over the past 50 years have undoubtedly also contributed to the eastern Karoo now having a higher grass vegetation cover than during the first half of the 20th century when sheep stocking rates were clearly unsustainable (Archer, 2004).

The brown locust prefers a habitat with a low grass and shrub vegetation cover, with plentiful bare ground patches available for basking and aggregation (Smit, 1939, 1960). The hypothesis made was that the denser grass cover has possibly made the former locust habitat in the eastern Karoo less optimal for the brown locust leading to fewer outbreaks in this area. The shift of the outbreak area further west into the Karoo is also supported by the fact that the former key locust control logistic depots at Middelburg in the eastern Karoo and at Kimberley in the north-east of the outbreak area were both closed down in the mid and late 1990s respectively, due to the recent history of relatively low locust activity in these areas (John Tladi, Deputy Director at DoA, *pers. comm.*). The brown locust control campaign management was then consolidated at the existing control depot at De Aar in the Upper Central Karoo, along with a new locust depot opened at Upington which now manages the more regular outbreaks occurring in the Gordonia district, and in the arid Bushmanland area in the western and north-western parts of the outbreak area.

6.2. 1995/96 season

Under the moderate intensity La Niña event of 1995/96, good widespread rains fell each month from September to December throughout the entire Karoo, with the ES of 1995 classified as wet to very wet in all sub-regions. This was considered to be the first 'wet' rainfall season in the western sub-region for 10 years. The first small-scale hatching was reported in the Victoria West (9 bands) and Richmond districts (6 bands) during late September and was soon followed in early October 1995 by a more intense outbreak in the Pofadder area in Kenhardt district (176 bands) and near Gamoep in the Namaqualand district (8 bands) in the western sub-region where large-sized hopper bands hatched from egg beds that had lain quiescent since March. The outbreak continued in the western sub-region during November and other isolated outbreaks were combated near Griekwastad, Hanover and Marydale. Despite the excellent rainfall, the scale of the 1st generation outbreak was smaller than expected and <1 000 bands were controlled before the end of December 1995. However, the first fledgling occurred from early December and by the end of January 1996 a total of at least 180 swarms were controlled in the Kaaibult area of the Kenhardt and Prieska districts, suggesting that the hopper campaign had stalled over the Christmas holiday season as often happens in the Karoo due to a lack of reporting from the farms which enabled hopper bands to evade being controlled. Approximately 40 swarms were also reported in the Gordonia and Hay districts in the northern sub-region at this time, along with a small outbreak reported in south-east Namibia near the Orange River.

2nd generation

The first hatchings of the 2nd generation were controlled in the Pofadder area in the western sub-region in late December, soon followed by new outbreaks in the Marydale, Kenhardt and Kakamas districts. By mid-February the 2nd generation hopper outbreak expanded to include most of western and central sub-regions (Fig.16), but the most intense control operations were undertaken in the area to the south of Marydale (Prieska district - 4 002 bands and 258 swarms) and in the Kakamas area (Kenhardt – 1 766 bands and 167 swarms), with 12-16 control teams in action. An intense outbreak was also being combated in the Gordonia district with >1 500 bands and 120 swarms being controlled. A total of 8,687 bands and 642 swarms were controlled during February 1996.

Although the LS 1996 was classified as being relatively dry for most of the Karoo, and very dry in the western sub-region, the Karoo was still lush and green as a result of the wet ES of 1995 which enabled the locusts to reproduce and for the outbreak to proceed unchecked. The hopper outbreak got out of control during March, especially in the Kenhardt-Pofadder area, in the Prieska-Marydale area and in the Gordonia district, and hundreds of immature swarms were observed migrating in various parts of the Karoo during March and April. Swarm displacements were mainly reported as south and southeast. A total of 14,563 bands and 2,647 swarms were controlled in March 1996.

3rd generation

Many of the migrating swarms from the 2nd generation were slow to mature eggs due to the prevailing dry conditions and a widespread 3rd generation failed to develop as had been expected. However, a localized 3rd generation did develop in the Pofadder, Kakamas, Kenhardt and Marydale areas with new hopper bands and resulting swarms being controlled during April and until mid-May. The hopper outbreak also continued in the Gordonia district well into May, with new swarms also being controlled. A total of 4,391 bands and 2,845 swarms were controlled in April 1996. Control teams continued to track down and control the migrating swarms throughout May in various areas of the Karoo, especially in the Britstown, Frazerburg and Victoria West (Loxton) districts, with nearly 250 swarms being controlled during May. The control campaign against the migrating swarms continued into early June.

The intensity of control operations against hopper bands is given as a colour-coded frequency map of the numbers of bands controlled per quarter (1/4) degree square (QDS) (Fig. 16). A total of 22 923 hopper bands were controlled during the 1995/96 season across 15 magisterial districts, with the heaviest infestations reported in the districts of Kenhardt (7, 331), Prieska (4, 376) bands) and Gordonia (1, 558 bands). The outbreak was very intense in some areas with >500 hopper bands being controlled in 15 individual quarter degree squares, with a maximum of 1 027 control actions reported in a single ¼ degree block.

Fig. 16. Frequency map of the location of chemical control operations against gregarious brown locust hopper bands per QDS during the 1995/96 outbreak season. Outbreak records for southern Namibia were not available for the mapping exercise. The revised outbreak area for the brown locust is shown.

Fig. 17. Frequency map of the location of chemical control operations against roosting adult brown locust swarms during the 1995/96 outbreak, per QDS. Outbreak records for southern Namibia were not available for the mapping exercise.

Chemical control operations against adult swarm targets are given as a colour-coded frequency map of the numbers of swarms controlled per quarter degree square (QDS) (Fig. 17). The number of swarms controlled increased dramatically from February to April 1996, with the heaviest control undertaken in the Kenhardt (2 720 swarms) and Prieska (1 259 swarms) districts. During the 1995/96 campaign, a total of 7 246 swarms were controlled in 16 magisterial districts across a wide area of the Karoo. The 1995/96 outbreak was considered to be of 'plague eruption' status as >5 000 adult swarms were controlled (Price, 2021). The swarm control operations were very intensive in some areas with >76 swarms being controlled in 35 individual QDS, with a maximum of 425 swarms controlled within a single QDS. However, a number of migrating swarms were presumed to have laid eggs before being controlled in May-June and a widespread hopper outbreak was forecast for the following early summer season.

6.3. 1996/97 season

The ES of 1996 was one of the wettest early summers on record and all sub-regions were classified as being wet to very wet, although only a weak La Niña to neutral ENSO condition was reported. The first hatchings were reported in the Calvinia (Brandvlei area) and Carnarvon districts in mid-September 1996 and a widespread hopper control campaign was soon being waged in 12 magisterial districts throughout the western and central sub-regions (especially in the Calvinia and Kenhardt districts in the west, and in the Colesburg, Victoria West and Philipstown districts in the central sub-region). A small hopper outbreak was also reported in the Gordonia district in the north. A total of 804 bands were controlled during September. The outbreak intensified during October and expanded to 16 magisterial districts, especially in the Carnarvon district (1 635 bands controlled), the Calvinia district (Brandvlei area with 1 173 bands controlled), the Victoria West district (1 121 bands) and in the Hanover district (1 003 bands), with many of these hopper bands being classified by locust officers as being large-sized and highly gregarized band targets. A total of 6 729 hopper bands were controlled during October 1996.

The hopper campaign expanded during November-December 1996 when up to 144 control teams were controlling between 4 000 and 6 000 hopper bands per week in 20 magisterial districts. However, heavy rains in November over a wide area of the Karoo hindered the control campaign and numerous fledgling swarms came onto the wing by the end of November and into December 1996. The November-December hopper campaign was very intense and was focused in the Carnarvon, Calvinia, Colesberg, Kenhardt, Hanover, Prieska and Victoria West districts, with >30 000 hopper bands and approximately 2 000 swarms being controlled in a massive control campaign across a wide area of the Nama Karoo. During late December 1996 and early January 1997, the swarms slowly migrated west and southwestwards on the easterly winds, but the prevailing wet conditions prevented the swarms from flying far and allowed the easy location and treatment of the swarms. Approximately 1 350 swarms were controlled during the first two weeks of January 1997.

2nd generation

The wet ES conditions favoured locust breeding and new hopper outbreaks were reported from a wide area across the central and western sub-regions by the second week of January 1997. The hopper outbreak was most intense in the Kenhardt, Prieska and Hopetown districts, as well as the Gordonia district. Adult swarms from the previous generation that fledged during November-December were also being controlled in many areas, especially in Britstown, Calvinia, Carnarvon, Colesberg, Gordonia, Philipstown and Prieska districts. During January 1997 a total of 7,915 bands and 2,120 swarms were controlled. The hopper control campaign continued to expand during February when up to 162 control teams were active in 28 Magisterial districts, especially in Prieska (Marydale) district (>3 800 bands) as well as the Britstown, Prieska, Philipstown and Victoria West districts in the central sub-region, in the Kenhardt district in the west, along with an intense hopper campaign being waged in the northern sub-region with >5 800 bands controlled in Gordonia district and 550 bands in Postmasburg district. The first fledgling swarms of this 2nd generation came onto the wing in early February and by the end of the month between 700-900 swarms were being controlled each week. A total of at least 16 860 bands and 2 577 swarms were controlled during February 1997. Most of the fledgling swarms were controlled in the Prieska, Hopetown and Philipstown districts. A number of swarms were also reported flying north and northeast, with some escaping control.

The remaining hopper bands continued to be controlled during March across the central sub-region, but the campaign intensified in the northern sub-region with >4 500 bands and >500

swarms being controlled in the Gordonia district, along with 385 hopper bands and 38 swarms controlled in the Postmasburg district. Rainfall totals for the LS 1997 were considered dry in the western sub-region but were normal to wet over most of the rest of the Karoo and very wet in the eastern sub-region. Conditions therefore remained very favourable for locust breeding well into the autumn, and the mature swarms from the 2nd generation that were observed migrating around the Karoo undoubtedly laid eggs before being controlled.

Fig. 18. Frequency map of the location of chemical control operations against brown locust hopper bands during the 1996/97 outbreak, per QDS. Outbreak records for southern Namibia were not available for the mapping exercise.

3rd generation

New hopper outbreaks were reported in late March and into April 1997 in the Hopetown, Strydenburg, Prieska, Marydale and Groblershoop areas. By the end of April, the control of hopper bands was being conducted over a wide area of the central, northern and eastern sub-regions, but the intensity of the hopper outbreak remained fairly low in most districts. Of continued concern was the ongoing outbreak in the southern Kalahari (Noenieput-Askam area) in the Gordonia district, where 5 483 hopper bands and 240 swarms were controlled during April. Swarms also flew into the Kenhardt district (Pofadder area) and some flew further west into the Namaqualand district, where 45 large swarms were controlled but no

local hopper control was reported that could have produced these swarms. A total of 7 597 bands and 468 swarms were controlled during April 1997, with the onset of the cold April night temperatures aiding the control operations against the roosting swarms. Control operations continued well into May against hopper bands and fledgling swarms in the Gordonia district, as well as in the Prieska district. The final swarms of the 1996/97 season were controlled in the Kenhardt district during the last week of May.

Fig. 19. Frequency map of the location of chemical control operations against brown locust adult swarms during the 1996/97 outbreak, per QDS.

TOTALS for 1996/97 season: 75,890 bands and 8,081 swarms. The 1996/97 plague season was a continuation of the plague cycle that started the previous 1995/96 season. The 1996/97 plague was widespread across the Karoo.

Possible 4th generation in the Gordonia district during 1996/97

A notable feature of the 1996/97 outbreak was the continuous locust activity in the Kalahari veld of the Gordonia district (northern sub-region) for each month from early September 1996 until late May 1997, with hopper bands reported throughout the entire nine months of the locust outbreak season. The Gordonia district experiences high summer temperatures

with daily maximum temperatures of >35°C and rainfall records show that this northern sub-region experienced wet conditions for both the ES of 1996 and the LS of 1997. Field conditions were therefore ideal for rapid brown locust development and reproduction throughout the locust season, with gregarious hoppers taking 5-6 weeks to develop and the fledgling adults then taking 2-3 weeks to lay their first egg pods in summer. It is highly probable that the brown locust was able to produce up to 4 generations in the Gordonia district during 1996/97. Monthly locust control records show the following:

1st generation: September (66 hopper bands), October (3 bands), November (179 bands), December (543 bands and 76 swarms). The 1st generation ended in mid-December when fledgling swarms were reported.

2nd generation: January 1997 (369 bands and 256 swarms), February (5,803 bands and 447 swarms). The 2nd generation was completed by mid-February 1997.

3rd and possible 4th generation: March (4,468 bands and 514 swarms), April (5,483 bands and 240 swarms), May (78 bands and 239 swarms). These figures indicate the occurrence of overlapping 3rd and 4th generations during March-May 1997.

6.4. 1997/98 season

A very strong El Niño event returned for 1997/98, and the ES of 1997 was exceptionally dry throughout the entire Karoo, especially in the western and central sub-regions. Drought conditions prevailed and the first light showers of spring were hardly enough to wet the soil in most areas. However, 20 small hopper bands were controlled in early September in the Hay district in the northern-sub-region, followed by eight bands in the Philipstown district in late September and one band near Colesberg. During October 1997 some more isolated hatching occurred, and a few small hopper bands were controlled in the Carnarvon, Phillipstown and Prieska districts in the central sub-region. A total of 56 hopper bands were controlled during September-October. Isolated hopper bands were then reported in the Hopetown and De Aar districts in November and December, as well as a hopper outbreak in the Gordonia and Hay districts, with 102 and 83 bands controlled respectively. Two small bands were also controlled in the Koffiefontein district in the eastern sub-region. A total of 33 swarms were controlled during December to the southwest of Upington (Kenhardt district) that had probably flown into this area as no hopper control was reported in Kenhardt district at that time.

The severe El Niño drought conditions continued across most of the Karoo and the LS of 1997/98 remained exceptionally dry in the western sub-region, and dry across the northern, central and southern sub-regions. However, the eastern sub-region received normal LS rainfall and the vegetation in this area was able to partially recover from the drought.

2nd generation

Control operations against scattered outbreaks started again at the end of January 1998 and continued into February 1998 at a low intensity over a wide area of the Karoo. Hopper bands were controlled in the Cavinia, Carnarvon and Williston districts of the western sub-region, in the Britstown, De Aar and Prieska districts in the central sub-region and also in the Gordonia district in the north. A total of 243 bands and 43 swarms were controlled during January and February. Control operations against hopper bands continued through March and into mid-April 1998, mainly in the Kenhardt district (Pofadder area) where 375 bands were controlled,

and in the Namaqualand district (42 bands), along with low numbers of bands also controlled in the Carnarvon, Prieska, Williston and Philipstown districts. The hopper control campaign was successful and virtually no swarms required control. The hopper campaign ended in mid-April at Van Wyksvlei in the Carnarvon district.

TOTALS for 1997/98 season: 1,018 bands and 80 swarms

Fig. 20. Frequency map of the location of chemical control operations against brown locust hopper bands during the 1997/98 outbreak, per QDS. Outbreak records for southern Namibia were not available for the mapping exercise.

Fig. 21. Frequency map of the location of chemical control operations against brown locust adult swarms during the 1997/98 outbreak, per QDS.

6.5. 1998/99 season

The ES of 1998/99 continued to be dry across the western sub-region, but winter and spring rains fell over most of the remainder of the Karoo and the ES rainfall conditions were considered to be normal in the northern, central and southern sub-regions and relatively wet in the eastern sub-region. However, the only records of locust control operations in this locust season were two small hopper bands controlled in the Kenhardt district (Pofadder East) in the first week of October 1998.

Despite a strong La Niña being in place for the summer 1999 rainfall areas of South Africa, the intense drought in the Karoo continued, and the LS rainfall conditions remained very dry in the western sub-region and dry across most of the rest of the Karoo. No further hopper outbreaks were reported, and no swarms were produced. There is no information available regarding whether any non-swarmling locust populations were present in the field. The total for the 1998/99 season: 2 bands and 0 swarms.

Fig. 22. Frequency map of the location of chemical control operations against brown locust hopper bands during the 1998/99 outbreak, per QDS.

No adult swarms were controlled during the 1998/99 season.

6.6. 1999/2000 season

The rainfall during the ES of the 1999/2000 season was very patchy across the western and central sub-regions with some of the rainfall stations receiving relatively high rainfall for these areas, while other stations remained relatively dry. However, under the strong La Niña event of 1999/2000 the average rainfall conditions across the Karoo for the ES of 1999 had improved substantially when compared with the ES of the previous two seasons of 1997/98 and 1998/99 and the drought condition had ended. Average rainfall across the western, central and eastern sub-regions were therefore considered to be normal, while it was wet in the southern sub-region and very wet in the northern sub-region. Despite the favourable rainfall conditions, no locust outbreaks were reported during the ES of 1999 up until the end of December. However, a low intensity hopper outbreak started from early January 2000 in the four districts of Britstown (20 bands), Kenhardt (76 bands), Murraysburg (25 bands), and Prieska (7 bands). The hopper campaign continued into February, with hopper bands again being controlled in low numbers in Britstown (3 bands), Murraysburg (10 bands) and Prieska (4 bands), along with new reports from Carnarvon (23 bands). The first adult swarms were

also controlled in the Carnarvon district (3 swarms), that were presumed to have flown in from the neighbouring Kenhardt district.

The rainfall conditions during the LS of 2000 remained normal to wet across the entire Karoo and the outbreak expanded greatly from early March 2000, with a 2nd hopper generation rapidly developing across a wide area of the Karoo. Numerous adult swarms also came onto the wing during this time. Control operations were focussed on the intense outbreaks in the magisterial districts of Kenhardt (12,871 bands, 491 swarms), Prieska (2,386 bands, 60 swarms), Gordonia (2,360 bands, 14 swarms), Britstown (374 bands, 51 swarms), Beaufort West (364 bands, 35 swarms), Calvinia (1,963 bands, 60 swarms) and Namaqualand (1,141 bands, 79 swarms). A total of 22,516 bands and 1,006 swarms were controlled during March 2000. Many of the hopper bands observed at this time in the Prieska and Kenhardt districts were highly gregarious, large-size band targets (Price, *pers. obs.*). Of interest was the occurrence of gregarious hopper bands and swarms well outside the recognised brown locust outbreak area, particularly in the citrus producing areas the of Ceres district (374 bands, 8 swarms) and further south in the Great Karoo at Laingsburg (34 bands, 4 swarms).

The intense campaign against the hopper bands continued throughout April with a possible 3rd hopper generation appearing on a small-scale in some western and central Karoo areas. However, more strategic focus was required on the control of the large number of adult swarms that had developed across the Karoo from the 2nd generation. The control figures from the following districts illustrate the scale of the campaign: Beaufort West (43 bands, 72 swarms), Britstown (74 bands, 310 swarms), Calvinia (2,557 bands, 88 swarms), Carnarvon (85 bands, 348 swarms), Ceres (170 bands, 113 swarms), Fraserburg (74 swarms – possible migration from Beaufort West), Gordonia (1,180 bands, 753 swarms), Hay (1 band, 1 swarm), Hopetown (0 bands, 15 swarms), Kenhardt (8,367 bands, 2,616 swarms), Laingsburg (4 bands, 6 swarms), Murraysburg (23 bands, 26 swarms), Namaqualand (5,165 bands, 800 swarms), Philipstown (8 swarms), Prieska (190 bands, 954 swarms), Richmond (30 swarms), Sutherland (12 swarms), Van Rhynsdorp (122 bands, 19 swarms), Victoria West (229 bands, 287 swarms), and Williston (100 bands, 69 swarms). A total of 18,310 bands and 7,393 swarms were controlled during April 2000.

During May 2000, the control campaign was predominantly focussed on tracking down and controlling the remaining adult swarms of the 2nd generation. Many of these swarms were now maturing and were starting to coalesce and migrate away from their fledgling sites and into neighbouring districts, which required a vigorous control campaign of tracking flying swarms during the day and then spraying throughout the night while the swarms were on their overnight roosts. There was also some control action against residual hopper bands in some of the districts. Control records give the following: Beaufort West (23 swarms), Britstown (107 swarms), Calvinia (109 bands, 186 swarms), Carnarvon (56 swarms), Ceres (20 bands), Fraserburg (12 swarms), Kenhardt (4 bands, 296 swarms), Murraysburg (13 swarms), Namaqualand (58 bands, 120 swarms), Philipstown (1 swarm), Prieska (41 swarms), Richmond (33 swarms), Sutherland (2 swarms), Van Rhynsdorp (6 bands), Victoria West (112 swarms), and Williston (32 swarms). A total of 197 bands and 1,034 swarms were controlled during May 2000. The hopper campaign had been completed by the end of May 2000, but the campaign against the remaining swarms continued until mid-August, which was unusually late in the season. During the period 1 June – 15 August, a total of 128 additional swarms were controlled, which had migrated in a southerly and south-easterly direction into the Murraysburg (59 swarms), Fraserburg (36 swarms) and Aberdeen districts (22 swarms).

Fig. 23. Hopper campaign for 1999/2000. Frequency map of the location of chemical control operations against brown locust hopper bands during the 1999/2000 outbreak per QDS. Outbreak records for southern Namibia were not available for the mapping exercise.

During the 1999/2000 season, the most intense control campaign against the hopper bands was waged in the districts of Kenhardt (21 318 bands), Namaqualand (6, 364 bands), Calvinia (4, 629 bands), Gordonia (3, 540 bands) and Prieska (2, 587 bands). A total of >100 hopper bands were controlled in 88 individual $\frac{1}{4}$ degree squares, with a maximum of 1 884 bands controlled within a single $\frac{1}{4}$ degree square (Fig. 23). Of interest was the hatching of gregarious hopper bands well outside the recognised outbreak area, and particularly in the citrus producing areas towards Ceres (564 bands controlled) in the Cape winelands of the Western Cape Province. The control campaign against adult swarms occurred from January to early August 2000, with a total of 9 565 swarms controlled during this plague eruption. The highest number of swarms were controlled in the Kenhardt (3, 403 swarms), Calvinia (1,126 swarms), Prieska (1, 056 swarms), Namaqualand (999 swarms) and Gordonia districts (767 swarms) with >50 swarms controlled in a total of 52 individual $\frac{1}{4}$ degree squares and a maximum of 491 swarms controlled in a single $\frac{1}{4}$ degree block. Swarms also originated from hopper outbreaks outside the recognised outbreak area hopper outbreaks outside in Ceres (121 swarms) and Aberdeen (22 swarms).

Fig. 24. Frequency map of the location of chemical control operations against roosting adult brown locust swarms during the 1999/2000 outbreak season, per QDS. Outbreak records for southern Namibia were not available for the mapping exercise.

TOTALS for 1999/00 season: 41,191 bands and 9,565 swarms controlled and therefore classified as a 'plague eruption' locust season based on the high number of swarms that developed. However, the ratio of hopper bands to adult swarms controlled during the season was 4.3: 1, which was considered to be below the average historical ratio, with the locust control campaign unable to initially contain the swarms before some were able to escape out of the outbreak area.

6.7. 2000/2001 season

The ES of 2000/01 was exceptionally dry across the western sub-region with an average of just 31 mm rain recorded across the ten rainfall stations included in this study. The ES rainfall in the central sub-region was very patchy, with some stations, such as Britstown and Prieska, remaining very dry (<50 mm rainfall), while other stations lying only 120-150 km to the east (Hopetown and Philipstown) received good ES rain and conditions were considered to be wet. Overall, the central sub-region received normal rainfall. Rainfall records for the southern sub-region were patchy and dry overall, while the northern sub-region received normal rainfall and the eastern sub-region was very wet.

Control operations started in the first week of September 2000 in the western districts of Calvinia (2 bands), Namaqualand (123 bands), and Van Rhynsdorp (99 bands). The outbreak then expanded with additional hopper control in Calvinia (191 bands), Murraysburg (2 bands), Namaqualand (437 bands), and Van Rhynsdorp (294 bands). The hopper campaign was particularly intense in the 'Voor Boesmanland' communal areas in Namaqualand where a high proportion of large-sized and highly gregarious bands were controlled. A total of 1,148 hopper bands were controlled during September 2000.

October 2000 saw a marked increase in locust reports and widespread control operations were undertaken against hopper bands across almost the entire Karoo, from van Rhynsdorp in the far west to Herbert in the northeast and from Namaqualand in the northwest to Aberdeen in the southeast. Control operations were undertaken in the following districts: Aberdeen (4 bands), Beaufort West (86 bands), Britstown (1,157 bands), Calvinia (336 bands), Carnarvon (400 bands), Clanwilliam (330 bands), De Aar (43 bands), Fraserburg (4 bands), Hanover (406 bands), Herbert (22 bands), Hopetown (1,084 bands), Kenhardt (122 bands), Murraysburg (753 bands), Namaqualand (891 bands), Prieska (700 bands), Richmond (1,228 bands), Van Rhynsdorp (198 bands), and Victoria West (1,474 bands). A total of 9,238 bands were controlled during October 2000, with intense control campaigns being waged in the Upper Karoo (central sub-region) districts of Britstown, Hopetown, Richmond and Victoria West.

During November and early December 2000, hoppers bands continued to be controlled over a wide area, with the first adult swarms coming onto the wing from mid November 2000. Districts affected included Beaufort West (41 bands), Britstown (664 bands), Calvinia (87 bands, 46 swarms), Carnarvon (213 bands), Clanwilliam (203 bands, 42 swarms), De Aar (37 bands), Fraserburg (1 band), Hanover (123 bands), Hopetown (645 bands), Kenhardt (15 bands), Murraysburg (308 bands), Namaqualand (51 bands), Prieska (274 bands), Richmond (958 bands), Victoria West (708 bands), and Williston (12 bands). A few large swarms started to coalesce and to migrate out of the Karoo, with 4 swarms controlled in Luckoff and 2 swarms in Griquatown. A total of 4,340 bands and 88 swarms were controlled during this period up until the end of December 2000 as the 1st generation of hoppers fledged and came onto the wing. Of note, was that there were very few reports of swarms being controlled across most of the ES 2000 outbreak, except in a very localised area of the Calvinia and Clanwilliam districts in the west and southwest (Fig. 26). This would indicate that the hopper control campaign was very effective and had contained the 1st generation outbreak at source.

Fig. 25. Frequency map of the location of chemical control operations against brown locust hopper bands during the 2000/2001 outbreak, per QDS. Outbreak records for southern Namibia were not available for the mapping exercise.

Rainfall conditions during the LS of 2021 remained patchy across the entire Karoo. The rainfall conditions improved slightly the western sub-region during the LS period, although conditions remained relatively dry. Rainfall conditions in the central and eastern sub-regions were considered normal, while it was dry in the southern sub-region and wet in the northern sub-region. Locust control operations started up again in the last week of January and into February 2021 in the western sub-region only, in the districts of Calvinia (45 bands, 5 swarms), Ceres (1 band, 10 swarms), Kenhardt (25 bands), and Williston (17 bands). The limited new hatchings were of a 2nd generation in this western sub-region. A total of 88 bands and 15 swarms were controlled during this period. However, there were no reports of the anticipated large-scale 2nd generation in the Central Upper Karoo and in the eastern Karoo, even though rainfall conditions were suitable for further breeding in these areas. It seems that the very effective control campaign against the 1st generation hoppers had eliminated the gregarious populations in these areas and prevented further breeding.

Fig. 26. Frequency map of the location of chemical control operations against roosting adult brown locust swarms during the 2000/2001 outbreak season, per QDS. Outbreak records for southern Namibia were not available for the mapping exercise.

The only reports received for March 2001 were from the Ceres district (21 swarms), Calvinia (9 swarms), and Williston (5 bands). Totals for March 2001 are 5 bands and 30 swarms. Widespread rains fell across most of the Karoo in April 2021 and autumn temperatures soon became too cold for further locust breeding. From 1 April to 6 May 2001, control operations were undertaken against the remaining locust targets in Calvinia (112 bands, 3 swarms), Kenhardt (8 bands), and Williston (29 bands). The campaign ended in Calvinia early May 2001. Totals for April and May 2001 were 149 bands and 3 swarms.

TOTALS for 2000/01 season: 14,968 bands and 136 swarms. Of interest during the 2000/01 outbreak was the hatching of hoppers in Aberdeen, Ceres, and Clanwilliam districts which are outside the recognised outbreak area, as these were probably the progeny from the 1999/2000 locust season where adults must have laid eggs before being controlled.

6.8. 2001/2002 season

Good rainfall conditions returned to many areas of the Karoo during the ES of 2001 and conditions were considered to be normal in the western sub-region, wet in the southern sub-region and very wet across the remainder of the Karoo (central, eastern and northern sub-regions). Average rainfall totals for the central and eastern sub-regions for this ES 2001 period were by far the highest totals for the current study since 1980. Control operations started in the first week of October 2001 and ended in the first week of November 2000. Only two districts were affected, namely Calvinia (637 bands, 61 swarms) and Ceres (1,268 bands, 76 swarms). This very localised outbreak was the progeny of egg beds laid by mature swarms from the previous outbreak in these areas in April and May 2001.

The LS of 2002 was dry throughout most of the Karoo, except for the eastern sub-region which was classified as having received normal rainfall for the late summer and autumn period. No further outbreaks developed during the 2001/02 season. There are no records of the status of the solitaria phase locust populations in the Karoo during the LS of 2002.

TOTALS for 2001/02 season: 1,905 bands and 137 swarms.

Fig. 27. Frequency map of the location of chemical control operations against brown locust hopper bands in South Africa during the 2001/2002 outbreak, per $\frac{1}{4}$ degree square.

Fig. 28. Frequency map of the location of chemical control operations against roosting adult brown locust swarms during the 2001/2002 outbreak season, per QDS.

6.9. 2002/2003 season

The ES of 2002/03 remained dry in the western sub-region, but wetter conditions returned to the rest of the Karoo with the central and southern sub-regions being classified as being wet, while the eastern sub-region was very wet. The northern sub-region received normal rainfall for the ES period. No locust outbreaks were reported during the ES 2002/03 despite the higher-than-average rainfall received across most of the outbreak area.

The LS of 2003 was influenced by a moderate-intensity El Niño summer event and drought conditions returned across a wide area of the Karoo, with the western sub-region being classified as being very dry and the central and southern sub-regions being dry. However, the eastern and northern sub-regions received more normal rainfall during the LS of 2003. No outbreaks were reported for the LS period.

TOTALS for 2001/02 season: 0 bands and 0 swarms.

6.10. 2003/2004 season

The drought conditions intensified during the ES of 2003/04, with the western and southern sub-regions being classified as being very dry, with the remainder of the outbreak area being dry. No outbreaks were reported during the ES of 2003/04.

The LS of 2004 remained generally dry, apart from scattered thunder showers falling in February and March. A relatively small-scale and localised hopper outbreak developed from late March into April 2004 in the two magisterial districts of Kenhardt (75 bands) and Prieska (42 bands), with a total of 117 hopper bands controlled. This outbreak was confined to the remote 'Kaiingbulte' area, which is a known high-frequency outbreak hot-spot area that lies to the east and southeast of Kenhardt town and into the Prieska district.

Fig. 29. Frequency map of the location of chemical control operations against brown locust hopper bands in South Africa during the 2003/04 outbreak, per $\frac{1}{4}$ degree square.

During the 2003/04 season, a total of 145 adult swarms were controlled during late April and May 2004 in the two magisterial districts of Kenhardt (109 swarms), and Prieska (36 swarms) (Fig.30). Although the outbreak was small and focussed in the 'Kaiingbulte' area, the control campaign was evidently undertaken late as indicated by the fact that more fledgling swarms being controlled (145) than the number of hopper bands controlled (117). The negative control ratio of 0.8: 1 band: swarms was unprecedentedly low, although the

swarm control operations during the cool autumn conditions did prevent the fledgling swarms from maturing and then escaping from the Kaiingbulte area.

Fig. 30. Frequency map of location of chemical control operations against adult brown locust swarms in South Africa during the 2003/04 outbreak season, per QDS.

6.11. 2004/2005 season

Locust control operations started in the second week of October 2004, with hopper controls in the districts of Kenhardt (1 band), Murraysburg (35 bands and Prieska (23 bands). Control of hopper bands continued through November and into the first week of December 2004 in Calvinia (14 bands, 1 swarm), Kenhardt (49 bands), Murraysburg (85 bands), Prieska (279 bands), and Williston (33 bands, 1 swarm). A total of 519 bands and 2 swarms were controlled from October until mid-December 2004. There are no further records of locust control during December 2004 and January 2005. A more substantial 2nd generation developed during February and continued until mid-March 2005 with control operations being undertaken in the districts of Calvinia (199 bands, 7 swarms), Namaqualand (378

bands, 10 swarms), and Prieska (68 bands, 1 swarm). A total of 645 bands and 18 swarms were controlled during the LS of 2005.

TOTALS for 2004/05 season: 1,164 bands and 20 swarms.

Fig. 31. Frequency map of the location of chemical control operations against brown locust hopper bands in South Africa during the 2004/05 outbreak, per QDS.

Fig. 32. Frequency map of location of chemical control operations against adult brown locust swarms in South Africa during the 2004/05 outbreak season, per QDS.

6.12. Summary of the brown locust outbreaks from 1995/96 to 2004/05

A summary of the brown locust outbreak/control information described for the decade period, 1995/96 to 2004/05 (as depicted in the ArcGIS maps above), is given in Table 6. The number of hopper bands and adult swarms controlled per season, the classification of the size and intensity of the different outbreaks and notes on the relevant field conditions are provided (Table 6). A brown locust 'plague eruption' season was defined when >5 000 adult swarms were controlled in the Karoo (Price, 2001).

Table 6. Brown locust outbreak summary information for the 10-year period 1995/96 to 2004/05.

Outbreak season	Number of hopper bands controlled	Number of adult swarms controlled	Classification of outbreak season	Notes on field conditions and control operations
1995/96	22 923	7 246	Plague eruption	High LS 1995 populations led to new plague in ES '95, most intense in Kenhardt and Prieska areas. Poor control in Dec.1995 and many swarms escaped. Intense hopper campaign in March 1996. LS of 1996 was dry, but plague continued.
1996/97	75 890	8 081	Ongoing intense plague	Very wet ES of '96. Intense campaign against large-size bands hatching from egg beds in the west. Hundreds of swarms in Jan. 1997 and widespread 2 nd & 3 rd generations. Continuous outbreaks in Gordonia district.
1997/98	1 018	80	Small-scale outbreak	Strong El Nino drought across the western and central Karoo. Plague collapsed and only limited hatching, along with vigorous control campaign. Drought continued into LS 1998 and only scattered outbreak.
1998/99	2	0	Recession	Good rainfall across the Karoo in ES '98, but virtually no hatching. The LS of '99 was dry, and no further outbreaks were reported.
1999/2000	14 191	9 565	Plague eruption	The dry ES of '99 and no outbreaks until end-Dec. Rain in Dec-Jan caused intense hopper outbreaks in western, central and northern Karoo. Next generation in March-April 2000 was highly gregarious, but control was unable to contain the swarms.
2000/01	14 968	136	Widespread medium-scale outbreak	Dry ES 2000, but widespread hatching from egg beds, mainly in western and central areas. Very effective hopper control prevented swarm development. Outbreak petered out in LS 2001.
2001/02	1 907	137	Localized small-scale outbreak	Good rains in ES 2001, but only small, localized outbreak from egg beds in Ceres and Calvinia area in October. The LS of 2002 was dry and no more outbreaks.
2002/03	0	0	Recession	Good rainfall in ES 2002, but no outbreaks. LS of 2003 was dry.
2003/04	117	145	Localized small-scale outbreak	The ES 2003 was very dry and there were no outbreaks. Small local outbreak in Kaiingbulte area in March-April 2004.
2004/05	1 164	20	Small-scale incipient outbreak	Scattered outbreak in ES 2004 in west/central regions. Larger hopper campaign in Calvinia and Namaqualand in LS of 2005.

6.13. Consolidated maps of brown locust control operations for 1995/96-2004/05

The database records for all the brown locust chemical control operations reported over the decade period 1995/96 to 2004/05 were consolidated into single maps (Figs. 33 & 34) for hopper bands and swarms respectively. The frequency of control operations is depicted as five frequency/intensity criteria, as shown by different colour indices.

Figure 33. Consolidated map of the intensity of control operations against gregarious brown locust hopper bands in South Africa over the decade period, 1995/96 to 2004/05, per QDS.

The consolidated hopper band control summary map clearly shows the high-frequency control areas, namely, in the western sub-region (i) around Pofadder in Bushmanland, especially in the areas around Pofadder and then east towards Kenhardt and northeast towards Upington; (ii) in the 'Kaiingbulte' area between Kenhardt, Prieska and Vanwyksvlei; (iii) in a third main area in the central/eastern sub-region between De Aar, Philipstown and Colesburg in the Upper Central Karoo, and also (iv) in Namaqualand to the northeast of Springbok town (Fig. 33). The intensity of control operations in some of these areas was very high, with >1 000 hopper bands controlled in 41 individual Quarter Degree Squares,

with a maximum of 2 711 hopper bands controlled in a single QDS during the decade study period. Although an individual QDS measures 27.76 km latitude and 21.84 km longitude = 606,28 km², these data still indicate a high insecticide load being applied almost annually in some specific QDS.

Fig. 34. Consolidated map of the intensity of control operations against adult brown locust swarms in South Africa over the decade period, 1995/96-2004/05, per QDS.

The consolidated control data against adult swarms for 1995/96 to 2004/05 (Fig. 34) shows that the highest frequency of swarm control occurred in the Kaiingbulte area, as well as to the northeast of Kenhardt towards Groblershoop. Another high-frequency area of swarm control was to the east of Carnarvon towards Britstown and south to Victoria West (Fig. 34). The intensity of swarm control operations in some areas was high, with >250 swarms controlled in 14 individual QDS, with a maximum of 654 swarms controlled in a single QDS.

7. Brown locust outbreaks

7.1. Brown locust outbreak frequency

A summary graph of the number of magisterial districts where chemical control action was undertaken against gregarious brown locust hopper band and swarm targets each season between 1960/1961 and 2004/2005, is shown in Fig. 35.

Fig. 35. Number of Magisterial Districts that reported brown locust control campaigns per locust season in South Africa, southern Namibia and Botswana between 1960/61 and 2004/05. Data obtained from annual reports of the South African National Department of Agriculture: Technical Services between 1960 and 1983, and from weekly/monthly locust control reports from the South African Department of Agriculture for the period 1984-2005.

Figure 35 shows the high annual frequency of brown locust outbreaks and the cyclical pattern of periods of wide-area locust swarming activity (such as when >10 districts infested) separated by periods of relatively low swarming activity (<10 districts infested). However, within the extended periods of wide-area locust activity there were also seasons when the ongoing outbreak cycle temporarily collapsed, usually due to prevailing drought periods, or as a result of effective control campaigns. There have also been the occasional wide-area incipient outbreaks occurring during the extended recession periods, such as the anomalous outbreak of 1981-1982. Figure 35 also clearly shows the occurrence of 'plague' periods within the ongoing outbreak cycles when >20 magisterial districts were infested.

7.2. Main outbreak districts

The database of records brown locust control operations undertaken during the decade period 1995/96 to 2004/05 was interrogated to define the numbers of control records and percentage of total records of control operations for the top 30 magisterial districts (Table 7). The database comprised approximately 20 500 control records in 41 magisterial districts.

Table 7. Number of brown locust control operations per magisterial district for the decade period, 1995/96 to 2004/05, giving total numbers and percentage of total for the top 30 magisterial districts.

Magisterial Dist.	Record counts	% of total control records
Kenhardt	3183	15,58%
Prieska	2717	13,30%
Carnarvon	1565	7,66%
Britstown	1490	7,29%
Victoria West	1471	7,20%
Gordonia	1351	6,61%
Hopetown	1234	6,04%
Calvinia	1084	5,31%
Namaqualand	697	3,41%
Hanover	686	3,36%
Williston	682	3,34%
Hay	594	2,91%
Colesberg	495	2,42%
Richmond	465	2,28%
De Aar	425	2,08%
Philipstown	361	1,77%
Murraysburg	320	1,57%
Herbert	271	1,33%
Fraserburg	263	1,29%
Postmasburg	255	1,25%
Fauresmith	185	0,91%
Ceres	133	0,65%
Beaufort West	120	0,59%
Noupoort	83	0,41%
Clanwilliam	75	0,37%
Van Rhynsdorp	68	0,33%
Jacobsdal	45	0,22%
Ganyesa	30	0,15%
Koffiefontein	12	0,06%

Table 7 confirms that most brown locust control operations during the 1995/96 to 2002/05 period took place in high-intensity outbreak districts of Kenhardt and Prieska, with a combined 29% of all records. The next highest frequencies occurred in the Carnarvon, Britstown and Victoria West districts, with approximately 7% of records each.

7.3. High frequency outbreak farms

The locust control database was also interrogated to highlight the top 3 high-frequency outbreak farms in each of the top 10 magisterial districts where brown locust control was undertaken. The names of the 'hot-spot' outbreak farms are given in table 8.

Table 8. Identification of 'hot-spot' outbreak farms with the highest frequency of brown locust control operations (both hoppers and adult swarms combined) in each of the top 10 outbreak magisterial districts over the decade period, 1995/96 to 2004/05, as derived from the brown locust control database. The names of the top three ranked outbreak farms in each of the districts is given.

Magisterial District	Farm Names
Kenhardt	ARREBEEES BANKSVLEI BLADGROND
Prieska	ROOIDAM GRASDAM POORTJIE
Carnarvon	TIERVLEI FORTUINSKOLK WITDAM
Britstown	HOLGATSFONTEIN LEEUKOPSPAN SOUTAAR
Victoria West	PAMPOENPOORT KAMEELBRON KALKFONTEIN
Gordonia	KAKAMAS WEIVELDE GROOT AARPAN KHORKHAM
Hopetown	ROOIDAM ELANDSBERG BOOMPLAAS
Calvinia	BRAKFONTEIN HOEK VAN PAN KATKOP
Namaqualand	KOUBERG NAIP KABIB
Hanover	VREDE NUWEFONTEIN RASFONTEIN

The list of the 'hot-spot' farms derived from the locust control database is valuable information for the planning of early-season field population surveys as a possible basis for an early warning system to monitor the development of incipient outbreaks of brown locust. Many of the farms listed above are already well known to some of the more experienced locust officers as hot-spot outbreak areas.

8. Discussion

Outbreaks of gregarious populations of the brown locust during the 45-year period 1960/61 to 2004/05 occurred very regularly in the semi-arid Nama Karoo region of South Africa and southern Namibia (Fig. 35). During the 45-year study period, only five seasons had no reported control operations, with virtually 90% of seasons (40/45 seasons) requiring the chemical control of at least some gregarious brown locust targets somewhere or other within the outbreak area (Fig. 35). Widespread and intense chemical control campaigns were required across at least 10 magisterial districts during a total of 26 seasons, which was 58% of the 45-year study period and highlights the high frequency and scale of brown locust outbreaks in the Nama Karoo.

As initially stated by Lea (1970) and later corroborated by Price (2021), the chemical control campaigns waged against the brown locust on an almost annual basis have evidently not dampened the ability of this locust species to produce serious eruptions on a regular basis, with enough of the gregarious populations surviving to lay eggs before winter to ensure the ongoing eruption into the next season (Price, 2021). Lea (1970) stated that it was evident from the control campaigns waged in the 1950s and 1960s that the preventative control action, in the sense of stopping the plagues from developing, had failed. Evidence from the current study largely agrees with Lea's conclusion.

The ever-increasing economic costs of the almost annual control campaigns, as well as the environmental contamination that is inevitably caused by the application of broad-spectrum insecticides in the ecologically sensitive Nama-Karoo biome is a cause for concern.

The cyclical pattern of brown locust outbreaks occurring over the 45-year study period are summarized below:

8.1. Outbreaks during the 15-year period, 1960/61 to 1974/75

The high swarming activity reported during this period comprised four distinct periods of intense outbreaks (plague eruptions) that lasted only two seasons each, namely, 1962/63-1963/64, 1966/67-1967/68, 1970/71-1971/72 and 1973/74-1974/75. Each of these short-lived plague eruptions was interspersed with short recession/dormant periods that also lasted only one or two seasons. Plagues were evidently stopped in their tracks by the onset of drought conditions in the Karoo, such as the LS drought of 1964, the drought of 1968 and again in 1972/73. However, more vigorous and effective locust control campaigns were generally waged during the second year of the plague eruptions which also played a vital part in containing the ongoing plagues, such as the campaign against migrating adult swarms in December 1963 and the campaigns against hopper bands in the LS of 1972 and again in LS 1975. De Villiers (1988) was convinced that the chemical control operations contributed significantly to the short two-year duration between different plagues observed during the 1960s and into the early 1970s followed by the two-year recessions or quiet periods with a low incidence of locust swarming.

8.2. Outbreaks during the decade period, 1975/76 to 1984/85

The plague of the previous 1974/75 season was brought under control by the combination of the effective control campaign during the LS of 1975 followed by the drought conditions experienced in the spring ES of 1975, with no outbreaks reported before January 1976. However, widespread incipient outbreaks soon returned in the LS of 1975/76 with a large-

scale hopper control campaign fought in LS of 1976 across 10 districts. This was followed by another successful hopper campaign in the ES early summer of 1976/77. This cycle of locust activity continued into ES of 1977 when another intense hopper campaign was fought, but the onset of extensive El Niño drought conditions during the LS of 1978 effectively stopped any further outbreaks. The extensive drought experienced in the Karoo from the late 1970s into the early 1980s kept the locust populations in recession (De Villiers, 1988). However, there were signs of ongoing build-up of incipient locust populations in different parts of the Karoo as a number of small-scale outbreaks were fought where the locust officers reported that the incipient hopper bands did not form concentrated targets for control and widespread 'opbouer' adult populations were also observed. In fact, these incipient populations did develop into a large-scale incipient outbreak during 1981-82 when good early summer rains triggered an outbreak with >10 000 hopper bands controlled across 18 magisterial districts. However, the drought returned, and the following 1982/83 and 1983/84 seasons remained dry with very few locusts reported. Better rains fell in the 1984/85 season and there was a widespread build-up of opbouer populations again during autumn of 1985, with control undertaken in 10 districts.

8.3. Outbreaks during the decade period, 1985/86 to 1994/95

This decade period was dominated by the massive plague eruption of 1985/86 which became the largest brown locust plague witnessed since the 1930s, with the peak infestation area stretching to >1 million km² across southern Africa. The plague was then dampened by the dry late summer 1986 field conditions, as well as the vigorous control campaign during autumn 1986. The phenomenon of the 'return migration' of the progeny swarms that bred in the central Kalahari in Botswana during winter 1986 and then flew back into South Africa, with a few swarms eventually travelling back to the prime breeding area in the eastern Karoo, was of great interest and provided a glimpse of the cyclical migration patterns undertaken by the uncontrolled plagues of brown locusts in the past before modern insecticides became available. There was widespread hatching in September-October 1986 from egg beds that had been laid by the migrating swarms the previous autumn across 51 magisterial districts, but the continuing drought into spring and early summer of 1986 combined with the very vigorous and effective hopper control campaign mounted during the ES of 1986 caused the plague to collapse by Christmas 1986. The LS of 1987 was dry, and no further outbreaks were reported.

During the 1987/88 outbreak, there were widespread reports of incipient hoppers from 18 districts especially from the central sub-region, but an effective hopper control campaign in the spring and early summer 1987 contained the outbreak. However, a relatively high ratio of swarms developed in autumn 1988 which indicated that the hopper control campaign had started too late and some swarms then laid eggs before winter. This was followed by another plague eruption during the wet season of 1988/89 across 40 districts of the Karoo with the control action being unable to prevent the development of >12 000 swarms and the long-distance migration of numerous swarms into the central and southern sub-regions. An intense hopper control campaign in the southern sub-region during the ES of 1989 prevented this large-scale outbreak from developing into another plague, but perhaps >200 swarms did escape and migrated north/northeast before being tracked down and controlled in the central sub-region. However, several dozens of these swarms escaped control and were then blown in an easterly direction on a strong weather front during mid-December 1989 that caused them to rapidly exit the Karoo and invade the interior of the Free State Province. Some swarms later invaded Lesotho in late December before being controlled. However, the intense ES 1989 hopper control campaign and the relatively few swarms that

survived to escape from the Karoo largely cleared the outbreak area of gregarious swarming populations and the LS of 1990 and the following dry 1990/91 season only saw small-scale outbreaks. However, during the LS autumn of 1991 the locust officers reported widespread incipient 'opbouer' populations, which was followed by an incipient outbreak in the spring ES of 1991. The hopper control campaign in ES of 1991 in the Great Karoo was considered ineffective as at least 1 000 swarms then developed in the Beaufort West district. Numerous swarms that survived control migrated north and northeast into the central sub-region, with several swarms eventually escaping the Karoo and flying over Kimberly and into the Free State Province and beyond during January-February 1992. A total of 37 districts were infested during the 1991/92 outbreak. However, the entire 1992/93 season was dry under a strong El Niño event and the locust population was dormant with only a small-scale hopper outbreak, hatching from egg beds laid by the migrating swarms the previous autumn, was reported on a few farms in the Britstown, De Aar and Hopetown districts during October 1992. The late summer and autumn of 1992/93 was very dry, and no further outbreaks were reported.

This short recession, however, was short-lived and another plague rapidly developed in the late summer of 1994 across 53 districts, especially in the central, western and northern sub-regions. The plague eruption of 1993/94 was first defined as a widespread incipient outbreak that rapidly gregarized to a plague situation in the summer of 1994, but it is not known if these swarming populations developed from incipient concentrations or perhaps from gregarious egg beds that had lain dormant in the soil for 18 months since the swarm migration event of February 1992. The rapid development of the plague situation in early summer 1994 was unexpected, as it was not previously considered that such an intense incipient outbreak could develop so rapidly after the widespread drought and low locust activity during the previous season. The standout characteristic of the 1993/94 plague was the intense outbreak experienced in the Bushmanland area and also the remote Kalahari sand veld area of the Gordonia district. Immense numbers of hopper bands and swarms developed in the Gordonia district and the outbreak here was continuous over a period of nine months from September 1993 to May 1994 with probably four generations completed.

During autumn and early winter 1994, numerous migrating swarms flew south and southeast into the Great Karoo and into the south-eastern Karoo where they laid a substantial number of egg beds before they were controlled during winter. The spring of the 1994/95 ES season started dry, and the early hatching was confined to the egg beds in the winter rainfall area of Namaqualand. The hatching of the overwintering eggs laid by the migrating swarms was delayed in the Great Karoo until more substantial rain fell in early summer. An intense hopper outbreak then developed in the Great Karoo during November and December with many swarms escaping control. Good summer rains across the western and central sub-regions in January 1995 then caused a widespread medium-scale outbreak in 33 districts, but the vigorous control action against the 2nd generation hoppers, along with the dry conditions in the western sub-region, kept the outbreak under control. However, there was widespread breeding across most of the Karoo and a new plague was expected for the following season.

8.4. Outbreaks during the decade period, 1995/96 to 2004/05

Field conditions were good for widespread locust breeding throughout the autumn of 1995, and the plague eruption status returned immediately in the ES of 1995/96 with intense hopper outbreaks in the Kenhardt and Prieska districts. The hopper control campaign faltered over December 1995, as is often the case when landowners are absent from the

farms during the Christmas holiday season when locust reporting falters and subsequent control capacity is not always available. As a result, many hundreds of swarms escaped control and the next hopper generations became very intense as the plague gathered strength, even though the late summer of 1996 was relatively dry. After winter, the wet field conditions of ES of 1996 caused the plague cycle to intensify further with an intense hopper campaign being waged, especially in the western sub-region where many large-size gregarious hopper bands hatched from egg beds deposited by swarms the previous autumn. Hundreds of swarms were present in the Karoo from January 1997 onwards and there was a widespread and intense 2nd and 3rd generations. Almost continuous outbreaks were combatted in the Kalahari veld in the Gordonias district.

During the 1997/98 season, a strong El Niño event caused drought conditions across the western and central Karoo. The on-going plague from the previous season quickly collapsed and the limited hatching of hopper bands were quickly controlled. The drought continued into LS 1998 and very few outbreaks were reported. Despite improved rainfall conditions in the ES of 1998, the locust populations were in recession. The LS of '99 was also dry, and the locust recession continued with only two scattered hopper bands reported. The drought continued through the ES of 1999 and was then broken by widespread rains in December 1999 and into January 2000. This widespread rainfall then initiated an intense hopper outbreak in the western, central and northern sub-regions of the Karoo. The next generation in March-April 2000 was highly gregarious and numerous large-sized hopper bands were reported. Unfortunately, control operations were unable to contain the hopper outbreak and numerous swarms (>9 500) escaped control and developed into a plague by the autumn of 2000. The spring of 2000 was relatively dry, but there was widespread hatching of bands from overwintering egg beds, mainly in western and central sub-regions. However, this season the very effective hopper control campaign prevented swarms from coming onto the wing and the outbreak petered out in the LS 2001.

Good rains fell in spring ES 2001, but the benefits of preventing swarms developing during the previous autumn resulted in only small and very localized outbreaks from overwintering egg beds in Ceres and Calvinia area in October 2001, which were quickly controlled. The LS of 2002 was dry, and no further outbreaks were reported that season. The locust populations were now in deep recession again and no outbreaks were reported during the ES of 2002 despite rainfall conditions being favourable over most areas. The LS of 2003 was relatively dry, and no outbreaks were therefore reported during the entire 2002/03 season. The ES 2003 was dry, and the locust populations remained in recession with no outbreaks reported. During the autumn of 2004 a small local outbreak was reported from the remote Kaiingbulte area in March-April 2004. Although this campaign was possibly a bit late in tracking down the swarms that had developed there were no reported swarm escapes from this outbreak. There was then a scattered incipient outbreak in ES 2004 in western and central sub-region, which was followed by a larger hopper campaign against incipient hopper concentrations in the Calvinia and Namaqualand districts in LS of 2005. The locust officers energetically tracked down these hopper concentrations and only 20 scattered fledgling swarms then required control.

8.5. Observations on locust outbreaks

1. The build-up of solitary 'opbouer' populations under favourable environmental conditions can occur almost simultaneously on hundreds of farms across a vast area of the Karoo.
2. The build-up of solitary 'opbouer' populations can occur concurrently, and entirely separately, from the on-going gregarious outbreaks. Incipient 'opbouer' concentrations can form loose hopper bands on the same farm and at the same time as gregarious hopper bands that hatched from egg beds laid by migrating swarms. There are thus two independent outbreak processes with entirely different ecology and population dynamics.
3. Smit (1939, 1960) showed that solitary populations in the Middelburg district slowly built up over at least seven locust generations before gregarious outbreaks ensued. However, in the current study the transition from scattered solitary populations to outbreaks of gregarious hopper bands sometimes took place within a season or two, which was far quicker than the previous generation timelines for the development of incipient outbreaks described in the literature. More field research is required on the population dynamics of the solitary phase of the brown locust, as advocated by Henschel *et. al.* (2023), particularly in the high-frequency outbreak areas in the central and western sub-regions.
4. The increase in average annual rainfall experienced in some of the western and central Karoo areas over the past 80 years has possibly enabled the outbreak area of the brown locust to expand westwards, as described by Kieser, Thackrah and Rosenberg (2002).
5. Farming activities in parts of the central and western sub-regions of the Karoo have possibly increased the 'prime' brown locust habitat available as the heavy grazing by sheep has caused more extensive short-grass habitats favoured by locusts for oviposition and for the aggregation of hoppers. However, in the wetter and more vegetated eastern sub-region, the general increase in grass cover over the past 50 years has reduced the open short-grass habitat area favourable for the brown locust and the status of the eastern Karoo magisterial districts as locust outbreak areas has declined.
6. The high-frequency outbreak areas, especially around Pofadder in Bushmanland and in the 'Kaiingbulte' area between Kenhardt, Priseka and van Wyksvlei, produce high numbers of large-size and highly gregarious hopper bands and swarms. Under favourable rainfall conditions, these remote and sparsely vegetated semi-desert areas enable the brown locust to breed rapidly and for the hopper bands to quickly aggregate and to gregarise into large-size hopper bands that demonstrate intense gregaria-phase behaviour traits of marching and roosting. These areas are therefore considered to be the key 'population driver' areas for the development of plague eruptions and where the really large swarms originate.
7. Conversely, the outbreaks experienced in the 3rd main high-frequency outbreak area of De-Aar-Hopetown-Philipstown, can be intense and more regular due to the more reliable rainfall experienced in this area. During outbreaks this area tends to produce large numbers of relatively small hopper band and swarm targets, compared to the large targets experienced in the western areas. This is probably due to the denser vegetation cover in this area of the eastern Karoo, which reduces the ability of the bands to aggregate and to intensely gregarise. In the opinion of the authors, this outbreak area

acts to 'seed' large areas of the Karoo with gregarious locusts, but it is not the main "driver" area that generates the largest plague eruptions.

8. In some seasons when the good early-summer rainfall enabled the first generation to develop successfully, the residual soil moisture and lush grass growth then continued to provide favourable field conditions for the locust outbreaks to continue unabated well into the late summer and autumn, even under severe late-season drought conditions.
9. Locust population increases and decreases are not primarily as a result of chemical control operations, but mainly whether the field conditions are favorable or not for locust breeding. However, weather conditions alone could not account for the rather regular periodicity of the plague cycles.

8.6. Observations on the efficacy of locust control campaigns

1. The 'Commando' system of ground-based locust control has been in operation for decades in the Karoo, employing temporary locust officers and teams of spray assistants depending upon the location and extent of the reported outbreaks.
2. The Commando system has provided a cost-effective control strategy against the unpredictable locust outbreaks and historically has been able to effectively manage small and medium-scale outbreaks of the brown locust in different parts of the Karoo.
3. Large-scale incipient outbreaks leading to plague eruptions occur rapidly and are largely synchronized over a vast area of the Nama Karoo. Such large-scale outbreaks are effectively unstoppable and often overwhelm the ground-based locust control capacity. Under these circumstances, the control campaigns can only endeavor to contain the outbreaks within the Karoo, as required by the South African locust management policy.
4. Well organized and effectively managed locust control campaigns can certainly hasten the decline of large-scale outbreaks and plagues, as occurred for example in the ES of 1963, the ES of 1974, the ES of 1986, the LS of 1995 and the ES of 2000. The effective control of the hopper bands and fledgling swarms is the key requirement to prevent the development and escape of migrating swarms.
5. However, some of the large-scale outbreaks and plague eruptions rapidly overwhelmed the control resources available and then effectively ran 'out of control' until the impact of late summer droughts or the onset of winter conditions brought the outbreaks to an end.
6. On some occasions it was evident that the control campaigns were initially disorganized and also started too late, so that outbreaks intensified and escaped the control operations. The result of the ineffective hopper control campaigns then allowed a high percentage of swarms to develop and to escape. These swarms then laid eggs before winter, which then became the source of the next outbreak the following season.
7. On some occasions, the next outbreak was well expected but the scale and extent of the outbreak was not correctly anticipated due to a lack of field intelligence about the locust populations. As a result, the control resources simply became overwhelmed by the intensity and wide distribution of the outbreaks.

8. The locust control campaign often takes too long to react to outbreaks in remote areas, such as in the western part of the Central Karoo and across Bushmanland, mainly due to the ineffective reporting of locusts on the large-size and often unoccupied farms in these areas. It then takes time to recruit spray teams and to transport pesticide and spray equipment to these remote areas, which sometimes allows the outbreaks to escape.
9. There is a serious lack of early warning systems for impending outbreaks, (i) no mapping of ongoing outbreaks is undertaken to determine where the migrating swarms in autumn are likely to lay their eggs that will then overwinter; (ii) field surveys of residual locust populations in autumn are not routinely undertaken to determine the scale and distribution of the incipient solitaria phase 'opbouer' adult population before winter; and (iii) there is a need for locust surveys after the first rains have fallen in spring, especially on some of the hot-spot farms with long history of outbreaks.
10. The control of concentrations of solitaria or transient phase opbouer adults in autumn as a means of reducing the prospect of gregarious outbreaks has been advocated in the past. However, the control such 'opbouer' concentrations, or the strip spraying of the Karoo veld with persistent insecticides for locust control, are not considered to be cost effective or environmentally acceptable.
11. The tracking down and spraying of thousands of individual hopper bands has long been considered as an inefficient use of manpower and resources. The targeting the hopper bands typically accounts for up to 90% of the locust control budget, but only accounts for 10% of the actual number of locusts controlled, whereas the targeted spraying of roosting adult swarms accounted for an estimated 90% of the locust population (Cilliers, van Someren-Greve and Lea, 1964; Price 2021). The switch of control tactics to using aircraft to control aggregating swarms has been advocated by Price (2021).
12. In recent years, the traditional Commando system has become more difficult to sustain due to the spiralling costs of transport and insecticides, as well as the costs of hiring the large temporary labour force required. The ongoing depopulation of farms in the more remote and arid areas of the Karoo means that there is a very low density of resident farmers left to report the locusts. In addition, the changing attitudes of some landholders towards reporting locusts due to their conservation views on the spraying of pesticides, or more especially regarding the security concerns on their farms, has therefore limited access to farms for locust surveys and has negatively impacted the efficacy of the locust reporting and control network. Outbreaks on the large-sized farms in the remote Central Karoo and Bushmanland areas therefore often go undetected, and the local control capacity can be suddenly overwhelmed by swarm escapes.
13. Alternative strategies of combatting outbreaks in the remote areas of the Karoo are required as an alternative to the current active location and spot spraying of individual locust targets. There is therefore a need to discuss possible alternative strategies based on sound economic and logistical principals and the use of drones and modern remote sensing technologies.

8.7. Research questions that still need to be answered

1. How does the concentration of egg banks laid by solitary phase locusts take place in time and space?
2. Contrary to the opinion of Botha (1967), can incipient solitary phase egg populations remain in diapause and quiescence for extended periods (>18 months) in the field to enable the egg populations to build up in the soil over a number of dry seasons across a wide area of the Karoo to then synchronously hatch when widespread rain falls to initiate immediate gregarious outbreaks?
3. Alternatively, is it the threshold density of 'opbouer' adults that is critical in the autumn season prior to incipient outbreaks developing in the following summer?
4. Why are incipient outbreaks more likely on the specific hot-spot farms? Are the habitats available on these farms more suitable for incipient outbreaks to develop?
5. Is "preventive" locust control possible? Is it practical and economically feasible to locate and destroy incipient swarming populations within the outbreak centers before they breed and form gregarious phase populations?

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